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Machine and deep learning applied to medical microwave imaging: a scoping review from reconstruction to classification

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Abstract

Microwave imaging (MWI) is a promising modality due to its non-invasive nature and lower cost compared to other medical imaging techniques. These characteristics make it a potential alternative to traditional imaging techniques. It has various medical applications, particularly explored in breast and brain imaging. Machine learning (ML) has also been increasingly used for medical applications. This paper provides a scoping review of the role of ML in MWI, focusing on two key areas: image reconstruction and classification. The reconstruction section discusses various ML algorithms used to enhance image quality, highlighting methods such as convolutional neural network and support vector machine. The classification section delves into the application of ML for distinguishing between different tissue types, including applications in breast cancer detection and neurological disorder classification. By analyzing the latest studies and methodologies, this review addresses the current state of ML-enhanced MWI and sheds light on its potential for clinical applications.

1. Introduction

Microwave imaging (MWI) is defined as the image of the internal composition of an object using electromagnetic fields within the microwave frequency range from 300 MHz to 30 GHz [1]. This imaging modality is possible due to the distinct dielectric properties of biological tissues within the microwave spectrum. The differentiation and imaging of tissues rely on their varying dielectric properties, particularly the significant contrast between tissues with high water content (such as tumor) and those with low water content (such as fat or bone) [2–4].

MWI in medical diagnostics offers notable advantages, particularly in breast and head imaging. Its appeal lies in cost-effectiveness, speed, non-ionizing characteristics, portability, and noninvasiveness. In breast imaging, MWI further stands out for its painless and less discomfort-inducing nature compared to conventional imaging techniques. Despite these benefits, the progress of MWI techniques has been delayed by hardware requirements and data quality. Encouragingly, recent advancements in wireless communication and computing technologies have paved the way for continued research and development in this field [4, 5].

MWI can be divided into two major types, microwave tomography (MWT) and radar MWI (rMWI). In both approaches, a set of antennas transmits low-power microwave signals into the body, and in turn, these antennas measure the scattered microwave signals [6]. MWT is a quantitative technique aimed at recovering the dielectric properties of an object from scattered signals. This methodology is mainly used with narrowband signals. The resulting image is obtained using iterative image reconstruction algorithms to solve a non-linear inverse scattering problem. This approach requires regularization with the aim of achieving convergence to a meaningful solution since they are affected by the ill-posed problem [6].

rMWI, also referred to as ultra-wideband (UWB) radar or Confocal MWI, is a qualitative technique that relies on the contrast of dielectric properties of various tissues, for instance the contrast between healthy and malignant tissue for the detection of cancerous tissue. The goal is to build an image that shows dielectric

variations without attempting to reconstruct the complete profile of dielectric properties [6]. The first algorithm for radar-based breast cancer detection was proposed by Hagness *et al* in 1998 [7, 8] and since then several algorithms have been proposed.

Over recent years, there has been a significant increase in the use of machine learning (ML) techniques within the field of MWI. ML, as an interdisciplinary area of artificial intelligence, focuses on developing algorithms capable of learning specific tasks across diverse research domains. In the context of MWI, ML has been applied to various tasks including image reconstruction, segmentation, and classification.

While several literature reviews have examined this topic, their scope and depth vary considerably. Patel *et al* (2022) [9] addresses only reconstruction tasks, discussing the application of ML at each stage of the reconstruction process, but limits its examples to breast imaging and does not provide a thorough comparison of different possible applications. Yago *et al* (2023) [10] focuses exclusively on deep learning applications, emphasizing the challenges associated with these approaches and presenting only two practical study examples. Khalid *et al* (2024) [11], while offering a more detailed article-by-article analysis, is already outdated since the most recent study considered was published in 2023; moreover, it lacks the range of coverage presented in this scoping review. Shao (2025) [12] is also less comprehensive, addressing both classification and reconstruction tasks with general details. In contrast, the our scoping review offers a more detailed analysis by not only examining the algorithms employed but also considering key aspects of the datasets, including size and the characteristics of the devices used for data acquisition. Moreover, our scoping review evaluates reported results and performance metrics given the specific tasks addressed in each study, offering a clearer assessment of methodological effectiveness and practical relevance. This comparative evaluation reveals key trends, limitations, and research gaps that have been previously overlooked or addressed only superficially, thereby underscoring the significance and contribution of this work.

This paper reviews the state of the art in the application of ML algorithms in MWI, with a focus on both image reconstruction and classification tasks, with either images or signals. The studies included in this comprehensive literature search were selected from three databases: Scopus, IEEE Xplore, and PubMed. The search strategy combined four thematic blocks using **AND** operators, and within each block, keywords were combined using **OR** operators:

- Microwave, UWB, MWI, ultra-wideband, ultra wideband
- Imaging, tomography, classification, detection, radar
- ML, deep learning, artificial intelligence, ML, deep learning (DL), AI, neural network, convolutional neural network (CNN), artificial neural network (ANN), U-Net, support vector machine (SVM), k-nearest neighbor (KNN), decision tree (DT), random forest (RF), SVM, DT, KNN
- Breast, brain, medical, diagnosis, diagnostics, disease, cancer, healthy, stroke

This search returned a total of 1200 records-769 from Scopus, 302 from IEEE Xplore, and 129 from PubMed. After removing 372 duplicates, 828 records remained for screening. Of these, 717 were excluded based on the following inclusion criteria:

- The study must involve MWI techniques as a central component.
- The ML algorithms must be applied to image reconstruction and/or be used for classification tasks.
- Classification tasks must involve clinically relevant classes, such as distinguishing between healthy and pathological conditions.
- The article must present experimental, simulated, or clinical results, rather than being purely theoretical or conceptual.

Additionally, 13 records were included to establish a baseline for classification performance using non-ML algorithms. In total, this scoping review comprises 124 studies, and the selection process, which was inspired by [13], is depicted in figure 1.

Figure 2 presents the distribution of the reviewed papers by application area. Among them, 37 focused on image reconstruction-22 on breast imaging, 14 on brain imaging, and one on leg imaging (not represented in the figure)-while 87 focused on classification tasks-62 on breast imaging and 25 on brain imaging.

Section 2 reviews ML applications for image reconstruction, with section 2.1 dedicated to breast cancer imaging and section 2.2 covering brain-related diseases such as brain cancer, Alzheimer's disease (AD), and stroke. Section 3 discusses ML-based classification, with section 3.1 focusing on breast disease classification and section 3.2 addressing brain-related conditions.

Sections 2.1, 3.1, and 3.2 organize the reviewed studies by algorithm type, separating them into ML and DL subsections. In cases where a study employs both ML and DL algorithms, it is presented in the ML subsection. This does not happen with the section 2.2, since all studies used DL algorithms.

Section 4 critically examines the reviewed studies, outlining current limitations, challenges, and opportunities in applying ML to MWI. It highlights the transition from classical ML models to deep learning approaches and emphasizes the need for larger, more diverse datasets, improved generalization, robust evaluation metrics, and greater replicability through public datasets.

Finally, section 5 summarizes the key findings of the scoping review, suggesting the potential of ML to enhance MWI-based diagnostics and suggesting future directions in clinical validation, dataset expansion, and the development of more robust, real-world-ready models.

2. Reconstruction using ML models

The use of ML algorithms to aid MWI reconstruction has been ongoing for over two decades, with one of the first studies being that of Rekanos *et al* [14], which present one of the first studies where they employ radial basis function neural network (RBFNN) to estimate the scatterer properties of tissues. Although their work did not focus on either brain or breast diseases, it is included here for its relevance. The RBFNNs were trained using the orthogonal least-squares algorithm, ensuring optimal network structure construction and straightforward determination of free parameters. The proposed methodology was employed in the estimation of the position and size of the proliferated marrow inside the bone of the lower part of the leg. The authors assumed the leg as a cylinder with a circular cross-section with a radius of 0.05 m and that the leg was irradiated from N antennas, and the scattered field was measured from L antennas. With the measurement configuration $N \times L$, three different measurement configurations were tested: 20×20 ,

Table 1. Overview of image reconstruction papers in the state of the art (Target zone: breast).

Reference	Algorithm	Microwave image type	Type of data
Kerhet <i>et al</i> [15]	SVM	Radar	Numerical
Ashtari <i>et al</i> [16]	NNRGA	Radar	Numerical
Conceição <i>et al</i> [17]	SVM	Radar	Numerical
Shah <i>et al</i> [18]	CNN	Tomography	Numerical
Khoshdel <i>et al</i> [19]	CNN	Tomography	Numerical
Khoshdel <i>et al</i> [20]	CNN	Tomography	Numerical
Mojabi <i>et al</i> [21]	CNN	Tomography	Numerical
Ambrosiano <i>et al</i> [22]	ANN	Tomography	Numerical
Mojabi <i>et al</i> [23]	CNN	Tomography	Numerical
Ambrosiano <i>et al</i> [24]	ANN	Tomography	Numerical
Ambrosiano <i>et al</i> [25]	ANN	Tomography	Numerical
Costanzo <i>et al</i> [26]	U-Net	Tomography	Numerical
Costanzo <i>et al</i> [27]	U-Net	Tomography	Numerical
Noël <i>et al</i> [28]	PG-SACC-CNN	Tomography	Numerical
Qin <i>et al</i> [29]	CNN	Tomography	Numerical
Fontaine <i>et al</i> [30]	CNN	Radar	Experimental
Bicer [31]	CV-MWINet, RV-MWINet	Radar	Experimental
Costanzo <i>et al</i> [32]	CVNN	Tomography	Numerical
Khoshdel <i>et al</i> [33]	CNN	Tomography	Numerical
Borghouts <i>et al</i> [34]	CNN	Tomography	Numerical
Franceschini <i>et al</i> [35]	ANN	Tomography	Numerical
Ambrosiano <i>et al</i> [36]	ANN	Tomography	Numerical

Artificial neural network (ANN), complex-valued combined model (CV-MWINet), complex-valued neural network (CVNN), convolutional neural network (CNN), neural network real genetic algorithm (NNRGA), physics-guided structurally-aware complex cascaded convolutional neural network (PG-SACC-CNN), real-valued combined model (RV-MWINet), support vector machines (SVM).

25 × 25, and 30 × 30. Gaussian noise was also added, with signal-to-noise ratios (SNRs) of 40, 35, 30, 25, and 20 dB, along with a noiseless case. In each of these datasets, the total number of samples, which in this study were the scattered-field measurements, is equal to 400. The study's results showcase the RBFNNs' precision in estimating the geometric properties of proliferated marrow. The best measurement configuration for low-noise or noiseless signals was 25 × 25, while for cases with high levels of noise, the best configuration was 30 × 30. The authors concluded that applying RBFNNs to medical imaging tasks, such as tissue characteristic estimation, holds promise due to their rapid estimation capabilities and resilience to noise. The study emphasized the importance of selecting an appropriate measurement configuration to balance information acquisition and noise impact.

2.1. Breast

Table 1 summarizes the papers on the application of ML algorithms to reconstruct breast images using MWI data.

2.1.1. ML

Kerhet *et al* [15] proposed a 3D approach using a SVMs classifier with a Gaussian kernel, to obtain the probability maps of tumor presence in a phantom of the breast. The approach was evaluated on synthetic data generated with the finite element method (FEM). The dataset used in this study contains 41 250 samples, each comprising 99 features: 96 time-steps of the signal and 3 geometrical coordinates of each pixel. Each sample is labeled with a binary class, where the positive class indicates a tumor-affected area, and the negative class represents a tumor-free area. There were 28 750 samples for the training set, 8750 samples for the validation set, and 3750 samples for the test set. All sets were scaled to a range from −1 to 1. The authors tested the approach in two different scenarios: one where the dielectric properties of the breast tissue were known *a priori*, and another where these properties were unknown. Additionally, the authors attempted training on a reduced dataset for the noiseless case of the first scenario. They reported that the probability maps obtained for the first scenario showed that the region near the tumor location tended to clearly stand out against the background. For the second scenario, they observed that although the quality of results was lower, the highest probability values corresponded to the tumor voxels. The specific method used to evaluate the model's performance was not reported, nor were objective results presented, making it unfeasible to ensure reproducibility or to draw conclusions supported by the model's performance.

Conceição *et al* (2017) [17] used an SVM to help in the diagnosis of breast cancer, while using a rMWI prototype developed at the University of Bristol. This study extends the authors' previous work [37]. In this study, 36 numerical phantoms were used, developed with layers of tissue mimicking materials. The model considered in the study consisted of 1558 synthetic focal points (SFPs), which corresponded to voxels in these numerical phantoms, comprising a total of 1925 455 measurements, classified as either 'hits' (tumor tissue) or 'misses' (healthy tissue) in the 36 numerical phantoms. Of the SFPs, 779 were 'hits' and 779 were 'misses.' An SVM classifier was trained using 24 features extracted from the signal of each SFP, aiming to distinguish between 'hits' and 'misses.' The dataset was divided into training and testing sets, and a k-fold cross-validation with $k = 10$ was implemented. The authors concluded that the SVM classification approach outperformed the linear discriminant analysis (LDA) classifier presented in their previous work [37].

2.1.2. Deep learning

Ashtari *et al* (2010) [16] proposed a neural network real genetic algorithm (NNRGA) for breast cancer detection using MWI. The dataset comprised 200 numerical breast profiles and 200 random profiles, which featured randomly distributed tissue types. The data were divided into training, validation, and test sets using a 60%/20%/20% split. Four breast tissue types were used in the study: mostly fatty, scattered fibroglandular, heterogeneously dense, and very dense. The NNRGA achieved its best permittivity reconstruction performance with the scattered fibroglandular breast type, reaching a relative error of just 2.7%.

Shah *et al* (2018) [18] employed a CNN to estimate the total electric field from the Born-approximated electric field, treating the problem as an image-to-image transformation. To train the network, the authors used a dataset composed of nine magnetic resonance imaging (MRI)-derived breast numerical phantoms from a public database [38], generating corresponding permittivity and conductivity maps. From these, 75% of the 2D coronal slices from seven randomly selected numerical phantoms were used for training, 25% for validation, and the remaining two numerical phantoms were reserved for testing. The images were normalized and had a resolution of 0.5 mm, while the simulated MWI images had a lower resolution of 1.5 mm. Training was performed using 33×33 image patches. This learning-based approach significantly reduced the l_2 distance between the predicted and true contrast distributions from 57.75 to 28, indicating its effectiveness in capturing the nonlinearities of MWI. The authors concluded that estimating the total electric field from the Born-approximated field using a CNN is a feasible and promising strategy for improving reconstruction accuracy in MWI.

Khoshdel *et al* (2019) [19] proposed a deep learning approach based on CNN to enhance MWI reconstructions in a dual-modality microwave-ultrasound system. The study employed 1200 numerically simulated breast phantoms, with half containing one tumor and the other half containing two. A hybrid reconstruction strategy was introduced, where the output of the contrast source inversion (CSI) method-augmented with ultrasound-derived tissue profiles-was used as input to the CNN. The CNN significantly outperformed CSI in both root mean square error (RMSE) and area under the ROC curve (AUC), achieving an RMSE of 0.122 and AUC of 0.987, compared to CSI's RMSE of 2.199 and AUC of 0.897. In a subsequent study, Khoshdel *et al* (2020) [20] extended this work to 3D MWI using a 10-channel 3D U-Net architecture trained on synthetic data. The dataset comprised 600 numerical breast phantoms with tumor diameters ranging from 1.1 to 1.5 cm, equally divided between single- and double-tumor cases. The CNN was trained on CSI reconstructions obtained using a FEM-based inversion and evaluated on both synthetic and experimental test sets. On synthetic data, the CNN achieved an AUC of 0.957 and RMSE of 1.161, while on experimental data, it obtained an AUC of 0.938 and RMSE of 1.172. In both cases, the CNN outperformed CSI, which achieved AUCs of 0.935 (synthetic) and 0.794 (experimental), and RMSEs of 1.436 and 1.250, respectively.

Mojabi *et al* (2020) [21] introduced a CNN with U-Net architecture to reconstruct MWI images from quantitative dielectric and/or ultrasonic property maps. The dataset included 400 numerical breast phantoms: 150 derived from 3D MRI intensity models capturing diverse fibroglandular patterns, and 250 from 2D MRI intensity models. Among these, 50 phantoms contained tumors across eight distinct configurations. The CNN was trained to map quantitative reconstructions of dielectric and/or ultrasonic properties to corresponding tissue-type and uncertainty maps. Although dataset partitioning was not specified, results showed that the CNN outperformed a Bayesian model in terms of the number of correctly classified pixels, highlighting improved accuracy in tissue classification. In follow-up work, Mojabi *et al* (2021) [23] employed two U-Net-based CNNs-one with two depth levels and the other with four-to predict the complex nonlinear relationship between ultrasound compressibility and dielectric properties. The two-level U-Net used 400 numerical phantoms derived from eight tumor-free, MRI-based breast models representing fatty, dense, and heterogeneous tissue types (350 for training, 50 for testing). The four-level U-Net dataset was augmented with 11 rotations at 30° intervals, expanding it to 4800 phantoms (4200 training, 600 testing). Inputs were ultrasound compressibility images reconstructed under the Born

approximation, and outputs were the real and imaginary parts of the true relative complex permittivity. The CNNs yielded predictions closely matching the true dielectric properties in both shape and magnitude, demonstrating their potential for generating accurate prior information for MWI algorithms. However, the study noted that training under the Born approximation may lead to the omission of tumor regions in some reconstructions.

More recently, Khoshdel *et al* (2023) [33] proposed a multi-branch CNN architecture to reconstruct two-dimensional permittivity maps for breast cancer detection using MWI. The model comprises two input branches—one for background tissue information and another for scattered field data—and was trained on 4800 synthetic 2D images generated from MRI-based numerical breast phantoms developed in earlier studies [21, 23]. While the data split was not disclosed, the test set included tumor-free, single-tumor, and two-tumor cases. Reconstruction quality was assessed through qualitative visual analysis, with the authors reporting that the CNN was effective in addressing the electromagnetic inverse scattering problem in breast MWI.

Ambrosanio *et al* (2020) [22] investigated the application of artificial neural network (ANN) for MWI of numerical breast phantoms containing tumors. A dataset of 50 000 numerically simulated breast profiles was employed, divided into training (80%), testing (15%), and validation (5%) sets. Although no quantitative metrics were reported, qualitative visual analysis revealed that the ANN-based reconstructions yielded superior tumor localization and contrast recovery compared to the traditional distorted born iterative method (DBIM). Building upon this work, Ambrosanio *et al* (2022) [24] explored ANN-based quantitative breast MWI using a dataset of 120 000 simulated profiles categorized into four breast tissue classes (A to D), ranging from predominantly adipose (Class A) to highly fibroglandular tissue (Class D). Data were split into 85% for training, 10% for validation, and 5% for testing. The ANN was evaluated against two conventional techniques, AMTISTA and CC-CSI, using structural similarity index measure (SSIM), normalized RMSE (NRMSE), and correlation coefficient (CORR) for both permittivity and conductivity reconstructions. The ANN outperformed both methods across all metrics and tissue classes for permittivity, and in most cases for conductivity, except for SSIM in Classes B and D, where CC-CSI slightly surpassed the ANN. The best ANN results for conductivity reconstruction were in Class D (SSIM: 0.417, NRMSE: 0.087, CORR: 0.871), while the highest SSIM for permittivity was in Class A (0.458), the lowest NRMSE in Classes A and B (0.102), and the highest CORR in Classes B and C (0.818). These outcomes highlight the ANN's capability to produce high-fidelity reconstructions across varying tissue compositions. A complementary study by Ambrosanio *et al* (2022) [25] employed a fully connected ANN trained on the same dataset (split 85%/10%/5%) to reconstruct both permittivity and conductivity, achieving NRMSE values of 0.10 and 0.26, respectively.

Borghouts *et al* (2023) [34] applied a CNN to image reconstruction and classification of breast MWI data into malignant or healthy categories. The dataset consisted of 160 000 simulated breast profiles, divided into 128 000 for training, and 16 000 for validation and 16 000 for testing, balanced across both classes. Reconstruction performance was assessed using Soft-Dice, normalized cross-correlation (NCC), and NRMSE, while classification performance was evaluated with accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, precision, and F1-score. The CNN achieved a Soft-Dice score of 0.144, NCC of 0.337, and NRMSE of 0.809. For classification, it demonstrated excellent performance, achieving 99.95% accuracy, 99.96% sensitivity, 99.94% specificity, 99.94% precision, and a 99.95% F1-score, confirming the potential of deep learning for end-to-end breast cancer detection in MWI. Using the same dataset, Franceschini *et al* (2023) [35] implemented an ANN for breast cancer detection, evaluating reconstruction performance on a pixel-wise basis resulting in accuracy (99.5%), sensitivity (98.9%), specificity (99.9%), and AUC (100%). Despite employing the same dataset as Borghouts *et al*, direct comparisons are limited due to differences in methodologies.

Extending their work, Ambrosanio *et al* (2024) [36] developed a fully connected ANN to generate tumor probability maps from breast MWI data. Using the same dataset of 160 000 simulated breast profiles (80% training, 10% validation, 10% testing), the model achieved a Soft-Dice score of 0.102, NCC of 0.287, and NRMSE of 0.856, indicating reasonable performance and reinforcing the utility of ANNs for probabilistic tumor localization in MWI.

Costanzo *et al* have published several studies utilizing data from the University of Wisconsin Computational Electromagnetics (UWCEM) repository [38], in which the output of the quadratic born iterative method (BIM) was used as input to ML models. In Costanzo *et al* (2022) [26], a CNN was employed; however, the total number of samples and the dataset partitioning were not fully disclosed. The CNN achieved a mean relative error of 8.09% and an average reconstruction accuracy of 91.91% across four different breast phantoms. In a complementary study from the same year, Costanzo *et al* (2022) [27] used a more controlled dataset consisting of 177 images from two numerical phantoms, with 95% of the images allocated for training and 5% for testing. The CNN achieved relative errors of 3.8% and 7.18% for low- and high-density phantoms, respectively. However, these results may reflect overfitting due to the small dataset size and limited phantom diversity. In subsequent work, Costanzo *et al* (2023) [32] introduced a

complex-valued neural network (CVNN) and compared its performance with two real-valued neural network (RVNN), one trained to reconstruct permittivity and the other conductivity. The dataset comprised 1500 images, divided into 80% for training and 20% for validation. The CVNN achieved a validation loss of 8.4205, closely matching the RVNN for permittivity (8.0074) and outperforming the RVNN for conductivity (16.2775), suggesting that the CVNN provides comparable or improved performance, particularly when handling complex-valued data.

Noël *et al* (2022) [28] proposed a physics-guided structurally-aware complex cascaded CNN (PG-SACC-CNN) for breast MWI, integrating both microwave and ultrasound modalities. The performance of the PG-SACC-CNN was compared to that of various CNN architectures, including a ResNet-based model. All networks were trained and tested using breast phantom data from the UWCEM repository [38]. The dataset included 2920 samples, divided into 2336 for training and 584 for testing. Network performance was assessed using Intersection over Union (IoU), reconstruction error, and SSIM. The PG-SACC-CNN achieved superior results across all metrics, with an IoU of 0.755, a reconstruction error of 0.156, and an SSIM of 0.810, indicating enhanced reconstruction accuracy and preservation of structural features.

Similarly, Qin *et al* (2022) [29] employed several CNN variants to jointly invert microwave and ultrasonic data for breast imaging, using the same UWCEM breast phantom dataset. In this case, the dataset comprised 2180 samples, with 1920 allocated for training and 240 for testing (there are 20 samples unaccounted for). Among the tested models, the CNN architecture that employed multistream input and multitask learning demonstrated the highest performance, achieving an IoU of 0.7504. These results further support the effectiveness of hybrid CNN-based strategies for multimodal breast imaging tasks.

Fontaine *et al* (2023) [30] used a CNN in a portable microwave system, aimed to reduce the device's cost, size, and complexity. The CNN was trained to directly reconstruct rod phantoms from their S_{11} sinograms. The training and testing data consisted of pairs of numerical rod phantoms and their corresponding S_{11} sinograms. In total, 10 000 phantoms were generated, but by randomly flipping and rotating the pairs, the dataset was expanded to 250 000 image-sinogram pairs. The entire dataset was then split into a training set (80%) and a test set (20%). The authors concluded that the CNN's predictions were promising compared to Delay-And-Sum reconstructions and that similar devices, using inexpensive materials, could serve as a viable alternative to conventional image reconstruction methods.

Bicer (2023) [31] evaluated four deep learning models for microwave radar-based breast imaging: a real-valued deep neural network (RV-DNN), a real-valued CNN (RV-CNN), a real-valued combined architecture (RV-MWINet), and a complex-valued combined model (CV-MWINet). The dataset consisted of 1000 scattered signals acquired from experimental breast phantoms. The RV-DNN and RV-CNN models were evaluated using mean squared error (MSE) and SSIM, while RV-MWINet and CV-MWINet were assessed using SSIM and classification accuracy. All models were evaluated with 10-fold cross-validation. The best performance was achieved by RV-MWINet and CV-MWINet, both attaining an SSIM of 0.999 and a classification accuracy of 99.3%. In comparison, the RV-DNN and RV-CNN models achieved SSIM values of 0.914 and 0.911, and MSE values of 197.401 and 162.089, respectively, demonstrating the higher performance of the combined architectures for both reconstruction and classification of breast tumor profiles.

Table 2 summarizes the characteristics of the acquisition systems employed in the studies discussed in this section. These include the number of antenna positions, the configuration of the acquisition system, the mobility of the antenna array, and the operating frequencies. The 'No. of antenna positions' column shows that most studies use setups with more than 15 antenna elements, commonly ranging from 20 to 30, with only a few exceptions reporting lower counts—such as the study by Kerhet *et al* (1 T and 16 R), Ashtari *et al* (4 T 16 R), and those by Costanzo *et al*, which used 10 or 18 antennas for both transmission and reflexion. The 'Multistatic vs Monostatic' column reveals a clear dominance of multistatic configurations, where each transmitted signal is received by all antennas in the array. Monostatic or quasi-multistatic (defined as the transmitted signal is received by all antennas except the transmitting one) systems are less common, and bistatic configurations appear rarely, as in Kerhet *et al*'s work. The 'Fixed vs moving' column highlights a strong incidence of fixed antenna systems, used in nearly all studies, with Bicer *et al* being the only example employing a moving array. The 'Frequencies' column indicates that 1 GHz is the most frequently used operating frequency across studies, although several works adopt broader or multiple frequency bands—such as Conceição *et al* (3–8 GHz), Fontaine *et al* (0.7–3 GHz), and Bicer *et al* (1–10 GHz)—to enhance imaging quality. Overall, the table reflects a consistent trend in the adoption of fixed, multistatic systems with moderate-to-high numbers of antenna elements and operating frequencies centered around 1 GHz. These choices suggest a growing consensus on hardware configurations that balance complexity, resolution, and practicality in breast MWI research.

Table 3 summarizes key characteristics of the datasets used in the reviewed studies. The 'Dataset' column describes both the dataset size and what the reported size refers to, which varies across works—for instance, it may represent the number of raw signal samples, image pairs, or patient profiles. This variability reflects the

Table 2. Summary table on the equipment used for microwave signal acquisition (Target Zone: Breast). Label ‘T’ represents transmitters, while ‘R’ represents receivers. When these labels are absent it means the respective study did not specify transmitters and receivers. The (*) indicates that the nomenclature used in this paper differs from that employed by the authors of the paper. ‘NA’ means not available.

Reference	No. of antenna positions	Monostatic vs multistatic	Moving vs fixed	Frequencies
Kerhet <i>et al</i> [15]	1 T 16 R	Bistatic	Fixed	6 GHz
Ashtari <i>et al</i> [16]	4 T 16 R	Multistatic	Fixed	1 GHz
Conceição <i>et al</i> [17]	60	Multistatic	Fixed	3–8 GHz
Shah <i>et al</i> [18]	24 T 24 R	Multistatic	Fixed	2 GHz
Khoshdel <i>et al</i> [19]	NA	Multistatic	NA	NA
Khoshdel <i>et al</i> [20]	24	Multistatic	Fixed	1.1–1.5 GHz
Mojabi <i>et al</i> [21]	30	Multistatic	Fixed	1, 1.5 and 2 GHz
Ambrosiano <i>et al</i> [22]	30	Quasi-multistatic*	Fixed	1 GHz
Mojabi <i>et al</i> [23]	30	Multistatic	Fixed	1 GHz
Ambrosiano <i>et al</i> [24]	30	Quasi-multistatic*	Fixed	0.2–1 GHz
Ambrosiano <i>et al</i> [25]	30	Quasi-multistatic*	Fixed	1 GHz
Costanzo <i>et al</i> [26]	18 T 18 R	Multistatic	Fixed	1 GHz
Costanzo <i>et al</i> [27]	18 T 18 R	Multistatic	Fixed	1 GHz
Noël <i>et al</i> [28]	20	Multistatic	Fixed	1 GHz
Qin <i>et al</i> [29]	20	Multistatic	Fixed	1 GHz
Fontaine <i>et al</i> [30]	26	Multistatic	Fixed	0.7–3 GHz
Bicer [31]	90 T 90 R	Monostatic	Moving	1–10 GHz
Costanzo <i>et al</i> [32]	NA	Multistatic	NA	NA
Khoshdel <i>et al</i> [33]	30	Multistatic	Fixed	1, 1.5 and 2 GHz
Borghouts <i>et al</i> [34]	30	Quasi-multistatic*	Fixed	NA
Franceschini <i>et al</i> [35]	30	Quasi-multistatic*	Fixed	1 GHz
Ambrosiano <i>et al</i> [36]	30	Quasi-multistatic*	Fixed	1 GHz

lack of standardization in how dataset size is reported. The ‘Input sample’ column specifies the actual data type provided to the model, such as scattered fields, dielectric profiles, or reconstructed images. The distinction between the ‘Dataset’ and ‘Input sample’ columns is necessary because most studies do not clearly define how many input samples are derived from the dataset. To address this, the table discriminates general dataset size from specific model inputs. The ‘Metric’ column reports the performance metric used and its corresponding value, with notable variation across studies. While some consistency exists, MSE and SSIM are frequently reported, other metrics such as IoU, AUC, accuracy, and *F1*-score also appear. The diversity in data types, input formats, and evaluation criteria highlights the heterogeneous nature of research in this domain. However, more recent studies tend to use larger datasets, more comprehensive performance metrics, and achieve higher accuracy or reconstruction quality, indicating a trend toward increasingly robust and data-driven approaches.

This section reveals a clear predominance of DL algorithms in breast image reconstruction tasks. Although synthetic (numerical) data remains more commonly used, several studies employing experimental data—such as phantom-based measurements—have reported promising results. Additionally, when comparisons are possible using the same evaluation metrics, there is a visible trend of improved performance as dataset sizes increase. These encouraging outcomes highlight the importance of continued development in this field. Advancing these applications will require the creation of larger and more diverse datasets, especially incorporating clinical data, to ensure that models are trained with information reflective of real-world conditions.

2.2. Brain

The articles that combined ML and MWI for the reconstruction of brain images associated with brain cancer, stroke and AD are summarized in table 4.

Xiao *et al* (2022) [39] introduced the hybrid neural network electromagnetic inversion scheme (HNNEMIS) for super-resolution 3D MWI of the brain. The proposed framework integrates shallow and DNN architectures by combining a semi-joint backpropagation neural network (SJ-BPNN) with a U-Net CNN. Two numerical scenarios were evaluated: one that involved normal brain imaging with a voxel resolution of $256 \times 256 \times 256$, and another focused on abnormal scatterer detection with a resolution of $512 \times 512 \times 512$. Each case used a training dataset of 200 samples and was evaluated under both noise-free and noisy conditions. The model achieved a reconstruction (model) misfit of 12.52%, and a data misfit of 0.73%, demonstrating its potential for high-resolution brain imaging.

Table 3. Summary of dataset characteristics and evaluation metrics from studies listed in table 1.

Reference	Dataset	Input sample	Metric
Kerhet <i>et al</i> [15]	41 250 (Signals and coordinates of the cell)	Signals and coordinates of the cell	NA
Ashtari <i>et al</i> [16]	200+200 (Breasts + random profiles)	FV	Relative error: 2.7%
Conceição <i>et al</i> [17]	1558 (SFPs)	Signal	NA
Shah <i>et al</i> [18]	NA	NA	L2 Distance: 28.54
Khoshdel <i>et al</i> [19]	1200 (Breast phantoms)	CSI reconstruction	RMSE, AUC: 0.122, 0.987
Khoshdel <i>et al</i> [20]	600 (Training set, breast phantoms)	CSI Reconstructions	RMSE, AUC (Syntetic, experimental): 1.161, 0.957; 1.172, 0.938
Mojabi <i>et al</i> [21]	400 (Breast phantoms)	Dielectric and/or ultrasound reconstructions	Overall error: 0.024
Ambrosiano <i>et al</i> [22]	50 000 (Breasts profiles)	Breast profiles	NA
Mojabi <i>et al</i> [23]	400, 4800 (Breast phantoms)	Reconstructed ultrasonic (Breast Compressibility)	MSE: 0.097, 0.038
Ambrosiano <i>et al</i> [24]	120 000 (Breast profiles)	Breast profiles	NRMSE, SSIM, CORR: (0.102, 0.458, 0.795
Ambrosiano <i>et al</i> [25]	120 000 (Breast profiles)	Breast profiles	NRMSE (Permittivity, conductivity): 0.10, 0.26
Costanzo <i>et al</i> [26]	NA	Quadratic BIM output	Acc, RE: 91.91%, 8.09%
Costanzo <i>et al</i> [27]	177 (BIM images)	Quadratic BIM output	Relative error: 3.87%
Noël <i>et al</i> [28]	2920 (Samples)	Scattered field	IoU, Error, SSIM: 0.755, 0.156, 0.810
Qin <i>et al</i> [29]	2180 (Samples)	Scattered field	IoU: 0.7504
Fontaine <i>et al</i> [30]	250 000 (Sinogram-image pairs)	Sinogram-image pairs	MSE, Accuracy: 0.137, 63%
Bicer [31]	1000 (Scattered fields)	Scattered field	Acc, SSIM: 99.3%, 99.9%
Costanzo <i>et al</i> [32]	1500 (Contrast maps)	Quadratic BIM output	Validation loss: 8.4205
Khoshdel <i>et al</i> [33]	4800 (Breast phantoms)	Scattered field	NA
Borghouts <i>et al</i> [34]	160 000 (Breast profiles)	Scattered field	Acc, Sen, Spe, Prec, F1: 99.95%, 99.96%, 99.94%, 99.94%, 99.95%
Franceschini <i>et al</i> [35]	160 000 (Breast profiles)	Scattered field	Acc, Sen, Spe, AUC: 99.5%, 98.9%, 99.9%, 100%
Ambrosanio <i>et al</i> [36]	160 000 (Breast profiles)	Breast profiles	NRMSE, NCC, Soft-DICE: 0.856, 0.287, 0.102

Accuracy (Acc), area under the curve (AUC), breast imaging modality (BIM), contrast-source inversion (CSI), correlation coefficient (CORR), *F1*-score (*F1*), Intersection over Union (IoU), mean squared error (MSE), not available (NA), normalized cross-correlation (NCC), normalized root mean square error (NRMSE), precision (Prec), relative error (RE), sensitivity (Sen), specificity (Spe), structural similarity index measure (SSIM).

From the same research group, Cheng *et al* (2022) [40] proposed a 3D Full Convolution Electromagnetic Reconstruction Neural Network (3D-FCERNN), supplemented by a U-Net-based image enhancement module. The 3D-FCERNN directly maps scattered field measurements to three-dimensional distributions of relative permittivity and conductivity, while the U-Net module refines the outputs to enhance image quality. Two cases were studied using simulated brain phantom data: the first with 190 healthy numerical phantoms ($256 \times 256 \times 256$ resolution) and the second with 250 unhealthy numerical phantoms ($512 \times 512 \times 512$ resolution). Both models were tested under various levels of Gaussian noise. The inclusion of the U-Net significantly improved imaging quality, particularly under high noise conditions (-10 to -40 dB). At -40 dB, the enhanced model achieved a 19.36% model misfit and 15.37% data misfit, outperforming the FCERNN alone.

Zhao *et al* (2022) [41] developed a ML-based inversion approach with resolution enhancement, incorporating a SJ-BPNN, a U-Net, and modified akima piecewise cubic hermite interpolation. The method was trained on 10 620 scattered field measurements derived from one numerical brain phantom. The resulting model achieved a 13.02% model misfit and a 5.7% data misfit, indicating effective reconstruction accuracy.

Xue *et al* (2024) [46] implemented a modified U-Net architecture, U-Net3++, for brain image reconstruction based on MWI. The study also compared the performance of alternative CNN architectures,

Table 4. Overview of image reconstruction papers in the state of the art (Target zone: brain).

Reference	Algorithm	Microwave image type	Type of data
Xiao <i>et al</i> [39]	SJ-BPNN + HNNEMIS	Tomography	Numerical
Cheng <i>et al</i> [40]	3D-FCERNN	Tomography	Numerical
Zhao <i>et al</i> [41]	SJ-BPNN, U-Net	Tomography	Numerical
Mousavi <i>et al</i> [42]	U-Net	Tomography	Numerical
Costanzo <i>et al</i> [43]	CNN	Tomography	Numerical
Costanzo <i>et al</i> [44]	CNN	Tomography	Numerical
Flores <i>et al</i> [45]	CNN	Tomography	Numerical
Xue <i>et al</i> [46]	U-Net	Tomography	Numerical
Zuo <i>et al</i> [47]	LEFEIM	Tomography	Numerical
Zuo <i>et al</i> [48]	LEFE	Tomography	Experimental
Costanzo <i>et al</i> [49]	CVNN	Tomography	Numerical
Xue <i>et al</i> [50]	U-Net	Tomography	Numerical
Movafagh <i>et al</i> [51]	U-Net	Tomography	Numerical
Mousavi <i>et al</i> [52]	U-Net	Tomography	Numerical

3D full convolution electromagnetic reconstruction neural network (3D-FCERNN), artificial neural network (ANN), complex-valued neural network (CVNN), convolutional neural network (CNN), hybrid neural network electromagnetic inversion scheme (HNNEMIS), learning electric field enhancement (LEFE), learning electric field enhancement imaging method (LEFEIM), semi-join back propagation neural network (SJ-BPNN).

including SegNet, U-Net, and U-Net++. Training was carried out using 100 two-dimensional numerical brain profiles, each containing a lesion located in one of five predefined positions (20 profiles per position). The test was performed on 150 profiles containing lesions (30 per position) and 30 healthy profiles. The models were evaluated using CORR, SSIM, RMSE, and peak SNR (PSNR). Although specific metric values were not reported, the results were presented as violin plots. Visual inspection of these graphs indicated that U-Net3++ consistently outperformed the other architectures in both healthy and unhealthy cases.

In a subsequent study, Xue *et al* (2025) [50] proposed a novel loss function-boundary-overlap-size (BOS) loss-for training U-Net++ networks aimed at reconstructing brain images containing anomalies. The model was trained on a dataset of 250 numerical brain profiles with abnormalities. Alongside the BOS loss, the network was also trained using MSE loss, SSIM loss, and a combined MSE+Dice similarity coefficient loss. Performance was assessed using accuracy, RMSE, and SSIM. The network trained with BOS loss achieved the best performance in terms of accuracy (91%) and SSIM (0.9973), and the second-best performance in RMSE (0.118), slightly worse than the network trained with MSE loss (0.113). These results demonstrated the effectiveness of the BOS loss in enhancing image reconstruction quality for MWI of brain anomalies.

Mousavi *et al* (2023) [42] proposed a U-Net-based approach to enhance the quality of MWT reconstructed brain images. The dataset consisted of 17 000 two-dimensional brain profiles generated from numerical phantoms, divided into a training set (12 000 samples), a validation set (2000 samples), and a test set (3000 samples). The proposed method was compared against the traditional DBIM imaging algorithm for two types of strokes: ischemic stroke (IS) and intracerebral hemorrhage (ICH). Evaluation metrics included the SSIM and the NRMSE for both permittivity and conductivity reconstructions. For IS, the proposed method significantly outperformed DBIM, achieving SSIM values of 0.4507 (permittivity) and 0.4533 (conductivity), compared to 0.0897 and 0.1521, respectively. NRMSE values were also lower (0.0607 and 0.1890 versus 0.1384 and 0.3864). Similarly, for ICH, the U-Net-based approach achieved higher SSIM values (0.4624 for permittivity and 0.4416 for conductivity) and lower NRMSE values (0.0557 and 0.1790), outperforming DBIM, which achieved 0.0934, 0.1739, 0.1393, and 0.3664, respectively. The authors concluded that these results indicate a substantial improvement in reconstruction quality using the proposed deep learning method. While this may hold true in comparison to traditional non-ML-based models, the claim is less convincing when compared to other ML-based approaches. For instance, the method proposed by Xue *et al* [50] achieved more than twice the SSIM, suggesting superior reconstruction performance.

In 2025, Mousavi *et al* [52] introduced an integrated reconstruction and classification approach for brain stroke imaging, with a primary focus on reconstruction. The dataset comprised 10 200 brain MWT images evenly distributed between IS and ICH cases. The proposed pipeline involved a U-Net for image reconstruction, followed by two CNN blocks for feature extraction (FE) and classification. The reconstruction performance of the U-Net was compared to an improved version of DBIM under various noise levels, using NRMSE and SSIM as evaluation metrics. The U-Net consistently outperformed DBIM across all noise levels and metrics, with the best results observed at 30 dB SNR for IS images, achieving an SSIM of 0.7887 and an NRMSE of 0.0523. In terms of classification, the highest accuracy was obtained at 10 dB SNR, reaching 99.5%.

Zuo *et al* (2024) [47] proposed the learning electric field enhancement imaging method (LEFEIM) for MWI reconstruction, which employs a two-stage cascaded deep learning framework. The first network predicts the electric field distribution based on measurements from the receiving antenna, and its output is then used as the input to a second network responsible for the final image reconstruction. The study used 19 experimental brain phantoms—one healthy, nine with IS, and nine with ICH. In addition to experimental data, simulated data were incorporated, although the total dataset size was not disclosed. The data were split into training (80%) and testing (20%) sets. LEFEIM was compared with three variants of the BIM, outperforming them in terms of relative error, achieving a low error rate of 1.07%.

In a related study, Zuo *et al* (2024) [48] introduced a method referred to as Learning Electric Field Enhancement (LEFE), which, based on its architecture, appears equivalent to LEFEIM, employing two cascaded neural networks for electric field prediction and image reconstruction. While the dataset size was not specified, LEFE was compared to the conventional BIM algorithm and demonstrated superior performance, achieving a RMSE of 2.96 and a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.93. These results further validate the effectiveness of the proposed learning-based framework for improving image quality in MWI.

Movafagh *et al* (2025) [51] proposed a hybrid reconstruction approach for brain MWI, combining an algorithm based on Huygens' principle with a U-Net architecture. Although the exact size of the dataset was not disclosed, it was generated from numerical brain phantoms affected by stroke. The results were presented as two reconstructed examples. However, no quantitative metrics were reported or referenced in the evaluation, limiting the ability to objectively assess the reconstruction quality.

Costanzo *et al* used data from the Zubal MRI repository [53] across several studies. In Costanzo *et al* (2023) [43], the authors investigated the performance of a CNN using two numerical brain phantoms with tumors: a simplified brain model and one derived from the Zubal dataset. The final dataset comprised 1800 variations—600 from the simplified model and 1200 from two slices of the Zubal phantom (600 each from slices 59 and 42). The data were split into 80% for training and 20% for validation. In all scenarios, the CNN significantly outperformed the quadratic BIM. For the simplified model, the CNN achieved an L2 norm of 6.98 compared to 81.46 for BIM; for slice 59, 5.81 vs 81.26; and for slice 42, 7.67 vs 82.32. In a separate study, Costanzo *et al* (2023) [44] applied a CNN to a dataset of 1400 brain profiles, also using an 80/20 train-test split. The CNN achieved an average relative error of 3.5%, further supporting the feasibility of deep learning approaches for brain MWI reconstruction using quadratic BIM output. In a follow-up study, Costanzo *et al* (2024) [49] proposed a CVNN trained on a dataset of 4400 images, again using an 80/20 split. The CVNN was designed to simultaneously reconstruct both permittivity and conductivity and was compared with two RVNN, each dedicated to reconstructing a single property. While the RVNN outperformed the CVNN for permittivity (MSE of 0.0032 vs 0.0036), the CVNN achieved superior results for conductivity (MSE of 0.0036 vs 0.0093), suggesting a more balanced and consistent reconstruction capability. A limitation is that in all of these studies, the models were trained and evaluated using data generated from a limited number of numerical phantoms, potentially compromising the generalization of the results making the models prone to overfit.

Flores *et al* (2023) [45] also used the Zubal MRI repository [53], alongside UWCEM [38], to train a CNN for cancer imaging reconstruction in both brain and breast models. The combined dataset comprised 500 images, with 95% used for training and 5% for validation. The CNN achieved a relative error of 2.35% for breast models and 5.5% for brain models, demonstrating the model's effectiveness across distinct anatomical regions.

Table 5 summarizes the characteristics of the acquisitions presented in the studies discussed in this section. The column 'No. of Antennas' shows that, similar to breast imaging, most studies use more than 15 antenna positions, with the exception of Costanzo *et al* (2024) [49], who employed 10 antennas as both transmitters and receivers. The 'Multistatic vs Monostatic' column reveals a higher incidence of multistatic systems, where transmitted signals are received by all antennas; all studies that reported this information used devices with this configuration. The 'Fixed vs Moving' column indicates that almost all studies used fixed antenna setups, with Movafagh *et al* [51] being the only exception. Regarding the 'Frequencies' column, most acquisitions were performed in the 0.3–2 GHz range, with 1 GHz being particularly common. The majority of studies used a single frequency, with two exceptions using a frequency range of 0.5–2 GHz by Xue *et al* [46, 50].

Table 6 presents an overview of the datasets and evaluation metrics used in recent brain image reconstruction studies. Most works rely on synthetic or phantom-based data, with dataset sizes ranging from a few hundred to over ten thousand samples. Input types vary across studies and include scattered fields, reconstructed images, and BIM outputs. Although some works clearly specify the number of input samples, others omit this information or provide only partial descriptions. Evaluation metrics also differ considerably: while RMSE, SSIM, and MSE are commonly reported, other studies use relative error, model misfit, or data

Table 5. Summary table on the equipment used for microwave signal acquisition (Target zone: brain). Label ‘T’ represents transmitters, while ‘R’ represents receivers. When these labels are absent, the respective study did not distinguish between transmitters and receivers. ‘NA’ means not available.

Reference	No. of antenna positions	Monostatic vs multistatic	Moving vs fixed	Frequencies
Xiao <i>et al</i> [39]	60	Multistatic	Fixed	0.3 GHz
Cheng <i>et al</i> [40]	60	Multistatic	Fixed	0.3 GHz
Zhao <i>et al</i> [41]	60	Multistatic	Fixed	0.3 GHz
Mousavi <i>et al</i> [42]	24	Multistatic	Fixed	0.85 GHz
Costanzo <i>et al</i> [43]	NA	NA	NA	1 GHz
Costanzo <i>et al</i> [44]	10 T 10 R	Multistatic	Fixed	1 GHz
Flores <i>et al</i> [45]	NA	NA	Fixed	1 GHz
Xue <i>et al</i> [46]	16	Multistatic	Fixed	0.5–2 GHz
Zuo <i>et al</i> [47]	16	Multistatic	Fixed	1.5 GHz
Zuo <i>et al</i> [48]	16	Multistatic	Fixed	1.5 GHz
Costanzo <i>et al</i> [49]	10 T 10 R	Multistatic	Fixed	1 GHz
Xue <i>et al</i> [50]	16	Multistatic	Fixed	0.5–2 GHz
Movafagh <i>et al</i> [51]	10 T 50 R	Multistatic	Moving	1 GHz
Mousavi <i>et al</i> [52]	24	Multistatic	Fixed	0.85 GHz

Table 6. Summary of dataset characteristics and evaluation metrics from studies listed in table 4. (*) The metrics are presented in violin plots.

Reference	Dataset	Input sample	Metric
Xiao <i>et al</i> [39]	200 (Brain Phantoms)	Scattered field	Model Misfit, Data Misfit: 13.63%, 3.68%
Cheng <i>et al</i> [40]	NA	NA	Model Misfit, Data Misfit: 19.36%, 15.37%
Zhao <i>et al</i> [41]	10 620 (Signal)	Scattered field	Model Misfit, Data Misfit: 13.02%, 5.7%
Mousavi <i>et al</i> [42]	17 000 (Images)	Images	NRMSE, SSIM: 0.0557, 0.4624
Costanzo <i>et al</i> [43]	1800 (Brain profiles)	Quadratic BIM output	Relative error, L2: 2.99%, 5.81%
Costanzo <i>et al</i> [44]	1400 (Brain Profiles)	Quadratic BIM output	Relative error: 3.5%
Flores <i>et al</i> [45]	128 (Breast/brain slices)	BIM Image	Relative error: 2.35%
Xue <i>et al</i> [46]	50, 150 (Brain 2D slices)	Signal	RMSE, SSIM, PSNR, CC: NA*
Zuo <i>et al</i> [47]	NA	Scattered field	Relative error: 1.07%
Zuo <i>et al</i> [48]	NA	Scattered field	RMSE: 2.96
Costanzo <i>et al</i> [49]	4400 (Brain images)	Quadratic BIM output	MSE: 0.0036
Xue <i>et al</i> [50]	250 (Brain 2D slices)	Signal	RMSE, SSIM: 0.113, 0.9970
Movafagh <i>et al</i> [51]	NA	HP images	NA
Mousavi <i>et al</i> [52]	10 200 (Images)	Images	NRMSE, SSIM: 0.0523, 0.7887

Born iterative method (BIM), correlation coefficient (CORR), Huygens principle (HP), mean square error (MSE), normalized root mean square error (NRMSE), not available (NA), peak signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR), root mean square error (RMSE), structural similarity index measure (SSIM).

misfit. Several studies report high SSIM values or low error rates, indicating good reconstruction performance.

Overall, deep learning methods dominate the selected studies and tend to achieve better results when larger datasets are used. Studies using reconstructed images or 2D signal slices generally report lower reconstruction errors compared to those relying solely on scattered fields. A few recent contributions stand out by combining high dataset volume with comprehensive evaluation, suggesting a trend toward more robust and scalable modeling. Nonetheless, the absence of clinical data and inconsistent reporting practices remain challenges for brain imaging.

3. Classification using ML models

ML has been used in the field of MWI for classification purposes for nearly twenty years, beginning with the work of Woten *et al* [54]. The classification tasks range from simpler distinctions, such as distinguishing

between benign and malignant tumors (MTs) in the breast [55], to other classification tasks, such as discerning between ICH and IS [56]. The studies present in this section use a variety of algorithms, as well as different types of data. The data used in these studies come from different sources: 1) computational simulation; 2) measurements made using experimental MWI prototypes and phantoms mimicking dielectric properties of tissues; 3) clinical studies, which represent the most advanced type of data.

3.1. Breast

Table 7 summarizes papers on the application of ML algorithms to classify breast images using MWI data.

The first article that used a ML algorithm in the classification of microwave images related to breast diseases was published by Woten *et al* 2007 [54]. However, it is important to note the contributions of Davis *et al* in 2008 [57] and Chen *et al* in 2009 [58], among others [59–63], in establishing a baseline regarding the performance of classification algorithms other than ML. Davis *et al* in 2008 [57] used a dataset comprising numerical target based on Gaussian random spheres (GRSs), replicating the irregularity of breast tumors. The authors used two basis selection methods from the literature: local discriminant bases and principal component analysis (PCA). Linear classifiers were constructed with the bases expansion vectors serving as input features, and the average rate of correct classification was evaluated as a performance measure. They demonstrated that for a SNR of 10 dB, the target size was reliably classified with over 97% accuracy, averaged over 360 targets, while target shape was classified with over 70% accuracy. Conceição *et al* [62] further contributed by creating a database that has been widely used in subsequent studies [64–67, 71, 73], which are reviewed in this article.

3.1.1. ML

In their study, Conceição *et al* (2010) [62] explored the application of an SVM model for the classification of tumors based on their radar target signature (RTS). The dataset included four distinct tumor shapes of varying sizes: spiculated, microlobulated, macrolobulated, and smooth GRS, with the former two representing MTs and the latter two representing benign tumors (BTs). Tumor shapes were manipulated by adjusting correlation angles and introducing spicules, resulting in a total of 352 tumor models across different sizes and shapes. Modeling of breast and tumor tissues was conducted using a 3D finite-difference time-domain (FDTD) approach, incorporating the dielectric properties of various tissue types. PCA was employed for FE, followed by dimensionality reduction to select the most significant principal components. Subsequently, SVMs were used to classify these principal components. The findings revealed that integrating a size classifier alongside a shape classifier yielded superior performance compared to using a shape classifier alone. Motivated by these results, the authors further investigated the impact of preceding size classification on the performance of shape classification, examining various combinations such as coarse-size-coarse-shape (CSCS), coarse-size-fine-shape, fine-size-coarse-shape (FSCS), and fine-size-fine-shape (FSFS). They observed a slight performance increase in shape classification when preceded by size classification. For instance, the coarse shape classifier attained its highest performance (90.62%) in the CSCS combination when preceded by a coarse size classifier. Similarly, the fine shape classifier achieved its peak performance (75.28%) in the FSFS combination when preceded by a fine size classifier.

Conceição *et al* 2011 [65] extended prior research conducted in [62, 64] by comparing PCA, independent component analysis (ICA), and discrete wavelet transform (DWT) for FE. They evaluated the performance of these methods with different classifiers (LDA, QDA, SVM) while introducing representative dielectric heterogeneity into FDTD simulations. Notably, the best results for each classifier were achieved as follows: LDA attained 89.1% accuracy with DWT, QDA reached 86.4% accuracy with DWT, and SVM achieved 93.0% accuracy with PCA [65]. It is worth noting that the SVM classifier produced the best results across all three FE methods, achieving 90.5% accuracy with ICA and 92.5% accuracy with DWT [65]. Another study that compared SVM and LDA algorithms was conducted by Santorelli *et al* (2014) [72], in which the feasibility of implementing classification algorithms for early-stage tumor detection was investigated. As expected, the results demonstrated that the SVM classifier outperformed the LDA classifier. This conclusion was also supported by the work of Santorelli *et al* (2014) [74] in which differential signals were used as input. Later, Gerazov *et al* (2017) [79] tested a deep learning approach using the same dataset as [65] and obtained 93.44% accuracy using DNN and CNN, which outperformed the conventional ML approaches, demonstrating the potential benefit of using deep learning for breast cancer detection.

The authors of [62, 64, 65] further examined the effects of dielectric heterogeneity in [66] by expanding their database to include 480 tumor models of various sizes and shapes. They employed PCA for FE and SVM for classification. Additionally, they evaluated two classification architectures, FSCS and FSFS, previously proposed in [62]. The study demonstrated consistent classification accuracy across different breast models used for tumor embedding. Introducing a fixed fibroglandular tissue structure resulted in minimal changes in accuracy compared to a homogeneous breast model, with FSCS accuracy decreasing

Table 7. Classification using machine learning models (Target zone: breast).

Reference	Algorithm	Type of data
Woten <i>et al</i> [54]	ANN	Numerical
Davis <i>et al</i> [57]	LDA	Numerical
Chen <i>et al</i> [58]	Customized algorithm	Numerical
Chen <i>et al</i> [59]	Customized algorithm	Numerical
Chen <i>et al</i> [60]	Customized algorithm	Numerical
Teo <i>et al</i> [61]	Customized algorithm	Numerical
Conceição <i>et al</i> [62]	SVM	Numerical
Kosmas <i>et al</i> [63]	Customized algorithm	Numerical
McGinley <i>et al</i> [64]	SNN	Numerical
Conceição <i>et al</i> [65]	LDA, QDA, SVM	Numerical
Conceição <i>et al</i> [66]	SVM	Numerical
O'Halloran <i>et al</i> [67]	SNN	Numerical
Yahya <i>et al</i> [68]	ANN	Numerical
Byrne <i>et al</i> [69]	SVM	Numerical
Byrne <i>et al</i> [70]	SVM	Numerical
Jones <i>et al</i> [71]	SOM	Numerical
Santorelli <i>et al</i> [72]	SVM, LDA	Experimental
Conceição <i>et al</i> [73]	LDA, QDA	Experimental
Santorelli <i>et al</i> [74]	SVM	Experimental
Reza <i>et al</i> [75]	SVM	Experimental
Conceição <i>et al</i> [76]	SVM	Experimental
Li <i>et al</i> [77]	2 ν -SVM	Experimental
Sacristán <i>et al</i> [78]	SVM, KNN	Numerical
Gerazov <i>et al</i> [79]	ANN	Experimental
Caorsi <i>et al</i> [80]	ANN	Numerical
Oliveira <i>et al</i> [81]	RF	Numerical
Aydin <i>et al</i> [82]	RF	Numerical
Aldhaeabi <i>et al</i> [83]	SVM	Numerical
Rana <i>et al</i> [84]	SVM, KNN, MLP	Clinical
Reimer <i>et al</i> [85]	MLP, SVM	Numerical
Hirose <i>et al</i> [86]	NN	Numerical
Conceição <i>et al</i> [55]	NB, DT, KNN	Numerical
Rana <i>et al</i> [87]	SVM	Clinical
Fasoula <i>et al</i> [88]	NB, QDA	Clinical
Chen <i>et al</i> [89]	SVM, DT, RF	Numerical
Liu <i>et al</i> [90]	SVM	Numerical
Sami <i>et al</i> [91]	SVM	Numerical
Patel <i>et al</i> [92]	LR, DT, RF, XGBoost	Numerical
Martins <i>et al</i> [93]	SVM, KNN	Experimental
Janjic <i>et al</i> [94]	Gradient Boosting	Clinical
Reimer <i>et al</i> [95]	CNN	Numerical
Janjic <i>et al</i> [96]	AdaBoost	Clinical
Papini <i>et al</i> [97]	RF and SVM	Clinical
Janjic <i>et al</i> [98]	SVM	Clinical
Halim <i>et al</i> [99]	PNN	Experimental
Lu <i>et al</i> [100]	CNN	Numerical
Ghavami <i>et al</i> [101]	SVM	Clinical
Rana <i>et al</i> [102]	SVM	Clinical
Abdelmawgood <i>et al</i> [103]	LR, SVM, NB, DT, XGBoost, AdaBoost, ANN	Numerical
Elnaggar <i>et al</i> [104]	DT, LR, RF, SVM, AdaBoost, XGBoost	Experimental
Eashour <i>et al</i> [105]	SVM	Numerical
Shadwell <i>et al</i> [106]	SVM	Clinical
Dridi <i>et al</i> [107]	SVM	Numerical
Ghosh <i>et al</i> [108]	AlexNet	Numerical
Taghipour-Gorjikotaie <i>et al</i> [109]	AEDPNN	Clinical

(Continued.)

Table 7. (Continued.)

Taghipour-Gorjikolaie <i>et al</i> [110]	SVM	Clinical
Patil <i>et al</i> [111]	LR, SVM, MLP, KNN, RF	Experimental
Pelicano <i>et al</i> [112]	SVM	Numerical
Yurtseven <i>et al</i> [113]	XGBoost	Clinical
Reimer <i>et al</i> [114]	LR, SVM, RF	Numerical
Tariq <i>et al</i> [115]	CNN	Numerical
Vijayarveswari <i>et al</i> [116]	SVM, DT, PNN, NB	Experimental

Artificial neural network (ANN), autoencoder decoder probabilistic neural network (AEDPNN), convolutional neural network (CNN), decision tree (DT), k-nearest neighbors (KNN), linear discriminant analysis (LDA), logistic regression (LR), multi-layer perceptron (MLP), Naïve Bayes (NB), neural network (NN), probabilistic neural network (PNN), quadratic discriminant analysis (QDA), random forest (RF), self-organizing maps (SOM), spiking neural network (SNN), support vector machine (SVM).

slightly from 79.57% to 78.13%, and FSFS accuracy increasing marginally from 63.48% to 64.57%. However, adding fibroglandular tissue clusters at varying locations modestly reduced performance, particularly with multiple clusters, where FSCS and FSFS accuracies dropped to 68.00% and 49.00%, respectively.

Byrne *et al* (2011) [69] proposed a breast cancer detection method using SVM and LDA. The dataset comprised 1728 signals (864 tumorous, 864 healthy) from numerical breast phantoms. The SVM achieved an overall accuracy of 83.66%, outperforming LDA by over 20 percentage points. Later, Byrne *et al* (2011) [70] extended this approach with a differential-scan method, where two consecutive UWB scans of the same breast were compared to detect tumor growth. The dataset consisted of 2880 samples, and performance was evaluated under different levels of tissue heterogeneity and tumor size. The differential SVM achieved 94.95% accuracy overall, significantly outperforming both the single-scan SVM (83.66%) and LDA (64.97%).

Reza *et al* (2014) [75] evaluated the performance of SVM and multilayer perceptron (MLP) models for breast tumor detection using simulated data. The dataset consisted of 300 samples, divided into a training and testing set using a 2:1 ratio. Among the samples, 264 were tumorous and 36 were healthy, resulting in a highly unbalanced dataset. The SVM model achieved perfect classification with 100% accuracy. In contrast, the MLP model performed poorly, with 54% accuracy, 100% sensitivity, and only 20.7% specificity.

Conceição *et al* conducted a series of studies using the same dataset comprising 3744 signals collected from 13 benign and 13 malignant breast tumors. Tumor shapes were modeled to approximate the GRS patterns adopted in previous works [62, 65], where spiculated and microlobulated geometries represented MTs, and round or oval shapes represented benign ones. The initial study [73] presented experimental results using a pre-clinical UWB prototype imaging system [117], and employed LDA and quadratic discriminant analysis (QDA) for tumor classification. A leave-one-out cross-validation strategy was applied, with the dataset divided into 13 groups of 144 signals each, enabling rigorous evaluation of classifier performance. The LDA and QDA models achieved classification accuracies of 87.10% and 89.34%, respectively. Building on this work, Conceição *et al* (2014) [76] applied an SVM classifier to the same dataset and reported an improved accuracy of 90.95%, surpassing both LDA and QDA. Later, Conceição *et al* (2020) [55] expanded the analysis by comparing the performance of Naïve Bayes (NB), DTs, and KNNs on the same dataset. Among these, KNN achieved the highest classification accuracy of 96.2%, outperforming all previously tested methods, including LDA, QDA, and SVM. These studies collectively demonstrate progressive improvements in classification performance as more advanced ML models were applied to the same underlying dataset.

Up to now, the most common ML algorithm in this section has been SVM. Li *et al* (2015) [77] used an adapted version of this method, the 2ν -SVM [118], which primarily aims to counter the effects of unbalanced training class sizes, to create a ‘cost-sensitive ensemble classifier’, consisting of three main components: FE, classification, and fusion. The authors constructed 9 experimental breast phantoms with different dielectric properties, with three of the phantoms being heterogeneous (containing glandular structures in 25%, 35%, and 50% of the total volume). By rotating these three phantoms by 120° , the authors created six new phantoms, resulting in a total of 15 phantoms. To simulate tumor and tumor-free cases, the authors inserted fat or tumor plugs. The signals obtained from the scans of the phantoms were divided into training data (signals from 13 phantoms) and test data (signals from 2 phantoms), resulting in 105 train-test combinations. The authors employed a 13-fold cross-validation to identify the best parameters. They reported the mean values and the 10% and 90% quantiles of different types of errors, with the mean value of the average error being 0.019, and the 10% and 90% quantiles being 0 and 0.05, respectively. In addition, the authors also present ROC curves, which support their conclusion that the proposed approaches outperform the delay multiply and sum based detection model. However, no further quantitative metrics are provided, making it challenging to compare their model with the other models and studies previously discussed in this section.

Sacristán *et al* (2016) [78] employed KNN and SVM models to classify simulated breast models as healthy or tumorous. Two distinct datasets were used: the first, referred to as the ‘Homogeneous’ dataset, included 1534 numerical breast models composed solely of skin and fatty tissue; the second, the ‘Heterogeneous’ dataset, consisted of 2395 breast numerical models containing additional fibro-glandular patches, with the fibro-glandular to fatty tissue ratio varying between 0% and 25%. In both datasets, 50% of the numerical models contained a tumor. The SVM models outperformed the KNN models in both cases, achieving 94% vs 73% accuracy, respectively, on the Homogeneous dataset, and 62% vs 57% on the Heterogeneous dataset.

Oliveira *et al* (2018) [81] applied a diagnostic architecture consisting of steps to create breast and tumor models, acquiring signals via FDTD simulation, followed by data processing, and finally, diagnosis. The breast models were derived from the repository created by the UWCEM laboratory [119]. The study used three heterogeneous breast models, with the percentage of glandular tissue ranging from 1% to 27%. For tumor models, the authors employed an algorithm from [120] to generate 72 unique tumor models, categorized into two classes: smooth borders representing BTs, and spiculated borders representing MTs. With a microwave device, 1080 microwave scans were performed, where each scan is composed of backscattered signals collected from 78 independent channels. The dataset used in this study comprised a total of 84 240 signals. Two methods, tumor windowing (TW) and FE, were used for signal processing. The classification was performed using RFs, applied to three types of classification models. The authors implemented a validation methodology based on nested cross-validation, and the performance of the classification model was assessed by plotting ROC curves. The AUC of the ROC Curve was also used to evaluate the model, as a higher AUC indicates a more generalizable model. The authors concluded that the models performed better when handling signals collected under consistent conditions. Furthermore, the data pre-processed solely with FE slightly outperformed those processed with TW + FE or only TW.

Aydin *et al* (2019) [82] applied a RF algorithm for breast cancer detection using data generated from a numerical hemispherical breast phantom. The dataset consisted of 400 samples, incorporating four different experimental conditions: with both matching liquid and tumor, with matching liquid but no tumor, with tumor but no matching liquid, and with neither. However, the paper did not disclose the distribution of samples across these categories. Model performance was evaluated using 10-fold cross-validation, yielding a mean classification accuracy of 94%.

Aldhaeabi *et al* (2019) [83] proposed a breast cancer detection method using ML algorithms, specifically SVM and DT classifiers. The dataset consisted of 90 numerical breast phantoms, evenly divided between H and NH cases. Among the models evaluated, the DT classifier achieved the best performance, with 65% accuracy, 68.8% precision, 55% recall, and 75% specificity.

MammoWave is a microwave device used for MWI acquisition and has supported several ML-based breast classification studies. Early work by Rana *et al* (2019) [84] used data from 18 subjects (12 H and 11 NH breasts) and tested KNN, SVM, and MLP classifiers with varying training set sizes. The best performance was achieved by SVM using 40% of the data, with 98.9% accuracy, 97.7% sensitivity, 99.7% specificity, and an Matthew’s CORR (MCC) of 0.955. In a later study, Rana *et al* (2021) [87] applied SVM to 61 breast scans (25 H, 36 NH), achieving 91% accuracy, 84.4% sensitivity, and 97.2% specificity.

Building on these efforts, Papini *et al* (2023) [97] conducted a more extensive clinical study on 697 breasts (123 NH, 574 H) using multiple classifiers (SVM, RF, DT, KNN, etc) with dimensionality reduction and class-balancing techniques. SVM and RF delivered the best results depending on the subset of data used: SVM achieved 88% accuracy, 86% sensitivity, and 89% specificity using raw data; RF reached 85% accuracy, 83% sensitivity, and 90% specificity for dense breasts; and SVM again showed the following results using image features (up to 87% accuracy and 88% specificity).

Ghavami *et al* (2023) [101] reported on the same dataset with 697 samples, using SVM to distinguish malignant from benign or tumor-free breasts, achieving 90% accuracy, 90% sensitivity, and 92% specificity.

Rana *et al* (2023) [102] used data from 61 breasts (35 malignant), with SVM again yielding improved results: 95.5% accuracy, 97.2% sensitivity, 94.5% specificity, and an MCC of 0.909.

In contrast, Shadwell *et al* (2024) [106] reported mixed outcomes: SVM reached 80% accuracy on a dataset of 352 breasts but dropped significantly to 44% on a separate set of 217 samples.

More recently, Taghipour-Gorjikolaie *et al* (2024) [110] an SVM achieved 64.49% accuracy, 61.25% sensitivity, and 65.08% specificity, with a larger dataset of 1024 breasts (161 non-healthy, 863 healthy). Overall, SVM has been the most widely used and successful algorithm across studies, consistently outperforming other classifiers, especially on smaller and more balanced datasets. However, performance tends to degrade on larger, unbalanced datasets, highlighting the need for robust data preprocessing and model selection.

Reimer *et al* (2019) [85] evaluated tumor detection performance using two ML models: SVM and MLP. Simulated data were generated from 2D numerical breast phantoms based on BI-RADS Class 1 and Class 2 tissue densities. Two datasets were used, comprising 2000 phantoms for Class 1 dataset and 2001 for Class 2

dataset, with 50% of each dataset containing malignant tissue. For both classes, two sub-datasets were created: one using data from a single rotational position (α) and another using data from five positions (β), resulting in different feature dimensionalities. The classifiers were trained using five preprocessing pipelines, and their performance was evaluated using accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, and the AUC. The best results were obtained with the (β) dataset. For Class 1, the SVM achieved 88% accuracy, 84% sensitivity, 92% specificity, and a ROC AUC of 95%, while for Class 2 it achieved 87%, 83%, 91%, and 94%, respectively. The MLP achieved similar results: for Class 1, 88% accuracy, 86% sensitivity, 90% specificity, and 94% ROC AUC; and for Class 2, 85% accuracy, 83% sensitivity, 86% specificity, and 92% ROC AUC. Across all classifier-dataset combinations, the feature scaling pipeline consistently yielded the best performance.

Fasoula *et al* (2021) [88] conducted a clinical investigation involving 25 symptomatic patients to explore the capability of the Wavelia semi-automated quantitative imaging function (QIF) in detecting and classifying breast lesions as malignant or benign. This study presents the methodology used in the Wavelia QIF to support breast lesion detection based on lesion persistence, sizing, and characterization within a feature space that encompasses both shape-based and texture-based features. The low-dimensional feature space covered shape-based features such as solidity, and texture-based features such as correlation and busyness. The features were extracted from the images. In the Wavelia QIF, a NB and QDA classifier were trained for the purpose of distinguishing between malignant and benign breast lesions. The results showed a notable level of separability between malignant and benign breast lesions, with a classification loss of 11.5% estimated using 10-fold cross-validation for the trained QDA classifier.

Chen *et al* (2021) [89] implemented SVM, DT and RF classifiers to distinguish between benign and malignant breast tumors using a two-dimensional numerical breast model. A total of 600 samples were generated, although the distribution between the two classes was not disclosed. The models were evaluated using both accuracy and *F1*-score. Among the three classifiers, the SVM model achieved the best performance, with an accuracy of 72.5% and an *F1*-score of 72.8%.

Liu *et al* (2021) [90] proposed a FE method based on ensemble empirical mode decomposition (EEMD) for breast tumor detection, evaluated using an SVM classifier. The numerical breast models were derived from four MRI images, yielding a dataset of 11 232 backscatter signal sets, with a balanced class distribution (healthy vs non-healthy) in a 1:1 ratio. The EEMD method involved iteratively adding white noise to the signal and applying empirical mode decomposition, resulting in several representative intrinsic mode function (IMF) components. FE was then applied to both the original signals and the IMFs, followed by dimensionality reduction using PCA before training and testing the classifier. The SVM achieved an accuracy of 84.5%. However, it is not possible to draw meaningful conclusions regarding the effectiveness of the EEMD-based approach, as no comparison with alternative FE methods was provided.

Martins *et al* (2021) [93] investigated the impact of antenna design on breast tumor detection performance using ML algorithms, specifically KNN, SVM, and LDA. Two antennas were tested: a Vivaldi antenna and a slot-based antenna. The dataset consisted of 480 measurements obtained from five experimental breast phantoms-240 without any tumor and 240 with one of two different tumor embedded. For the slot-based antenna, classification accuracies were 60% for KNN, and 50% for both SVM and LDA. In contrast, the Vivaldi antenna yielded significantly higher performance, with 80% accuracy for KNN, 70% for SVM, and 85% for LDA, demonstrating a clear advantage of the Vivaldi design over the slot-based alternative, which indicates that antenna design may have an impact on classification results.

Reimer *et al* (2020) [121] developed an open-source dataset for breast microwave MWI, which has been widely adopted for evaluating ML approaches to breast tumor detection. The dataset is divided into three generations: the first comprises 249 experimental scans, the second includes 1008 scans, and the third contains 200 scans. While the first two generations were reported in the original publication [121], a third generation was introduced later by Reimer *et al* (2021) [122].

Sami *et al* (2021) [91] used the second-generation dataset of 1008 scans-800 for training and 208 for cross-validation-to train an SVM model, achieving outstanding results: 99.7% accuracy, 99.2% sensitivity, and 99.9% specificity.

Patel *et al* (2021) [92] employed a subset of 249 scans to compare DT, RF, and XGBoost models. The RF model achieved the best performance among these, with 94% accuracy, 100% sensitivity, and 89.2% specificity; however, none of the models matched the performance of the SVM reported by Sami *et al* (2021) [91].

Dridi *et al* (2024) [107] evaluated linear and RBF-kernel SVMs, as well as logistic regression (LR), on a subset of 249 scans (199 for training and 50 for testing). The linear SVM achieved the best results in this study, with 98% accuracy, 96.15% sensitivity, and 100% specificity.

Reimer *et al* (2025) [114] employed the third-generation dataset of 200 scans (150 for training and 50 for testing) to train LR, SVM, and RF models using features extracted from reconstructed images. Although multiple combinations of classifiers and reconstruction methods were tested, the study did not report

specific AUC values. In summary, using accuracy as the comparison metric, the best results were obtained in studies that used a single dataset generation, with the highest performance achieved by Sami *et al* [91] using the second generation, which likely corresponds to a real case scenario where data variability is present. The study based on the third generation, reported by Reimer *et al* [114], did not disclose objective performance metrics, making direct comparisons with the other generations infeasible.

Another microwave device used for MWI acquisition and ML-based classification is the Scan and Find Early (SAFE) system, which has been employed in several clinical studies. Janjic *et al* (2022) [94] first evaluated the device using backscattered signals from 54 patients with breast lesions (29 benign and 25 malignant), applying a gradient boosting algorithm that achieved 81% accuracy, 80% sensitivity, and 83% specificity. Building on this, Janjic *et al* (2023) [96] expanded the dataset to 113 samples (70 benign, 43 malignant), collected from BI-RADS 4 and 5 patients, and used an AdaBoost classifier, which resulted in slightly lower performance: 78% accuracy, 79% sensitivity, and 77% specificity. In a more extensive clinical study, Janjic *et al* (2023) [98] analyzed 558 breast samples (390 from healthy subjects and 168 from cancer patients) using an SVM classifier, reporting significantly improved outcomes with 93% accuracy, 95% sensitivity, and 92% specificity.

Similarly, Yurtseven *et al* (2025) [113] assessed the SAFE device on 526 cases (286 non-cancerous and 240 malignant), employing an XGBoost model that achieved its best performance on dense breast tissue, with 91% accuracy, 91% sensitivity, and 92% specificity. Collectively, these studies highlight the SAFE device's growing clinical relevance, with progressively larger datasets and more advanced classifiers yielding higher diagnostic performance.

Abdelmawgood *et al* (2023) [103] proposed a tumor detection framework based on textile antenna sensors and ML algorithms, including LR, SVM, NB, DT, XGBoost, AdaBoost, CatBoost, and ANN. The dataset was generated using a three-layer numerical breast phantom consisting of fat, fibroglandular, and skin tissues. It comprised 1001 samples, balanced between healthy and malignant cases, although the class distribution was not explicitly detailed. The dataset was split into training and test sets using a 70/30 ratio. Results were reported for two tumor configurations: two centered tumors and one shifted tumor. However, it was not clearly stated whether 1001 samples were used per configuration or in total. The best performance was achieved by XGBoost for the 5 mm centered tumor case, with an accuracy of 99%. The worst performance was observed with NB, which achieved only 49% accuracy for both the 5 mm centered and shifted tumor cases. These results highlight the potential of using XGBoost in wearable systems, such as a smart bra, for breast tumor detection using ML. However, the high performance reported may be the result of overfitting, as the data were obtained from a single phantom, limiting the generalization of the findings.

Elnaggar *et al* (2024) [104] proposed a wearable textile-based bra-tenna system for breast cancer detection, integrating UWB microwave sensing with ML algorithms. The classifiers evaluated included SVM, RF, gradient boosting machine, DT, AdaBoost, CatBoost, XGBoost, and LR. Two classification scenarios were studied: binary classification (healthy vs non-healthy) and multiclass classification (healthy, one tumor, and two tumors). The binary dataset comprised 1602 samples, and the multiclass dataset 2403 samples—both evenly distributed across classes. In the binary scenario, SVM achieved the best performance with 98% accuracy, 98% precision, 98% recall, 98% *F1*-score, and an AUC of 1.00. In the multiclass scenario, SVM again outperformed all other models, reaching 99% accuracy, 98.67% precision, 98.67% recall, and 98.67% *F1*-score.

Patil *et al* (2024) [111] evaluated the performance of five ML algorithms—LR, SVM, MLP, KNN, and RF—for breast tumor detection. The dataset consisted of 804 feature vectors obtained from measurements on experimental breast phantoms. The class distribution was not disclosed. The dataset was split into training and test sets using a 70/30 ratio. Among the tested models, RF achieved the best performance, with 98.04% accuracy, 96.72% sensitivity, 96.67% specificity, 96.72% precision, 96.72% *F1*-score, and an AUC of 98.05%.

Pelicano *et al* (2025) [112] investigated whether the complexity of breast phantoms affects the classification performance between benign and MTs. A total of eight numerical breast phantoms were used, from which 830 backscattered signals were collected, 460 benign and 370 malignant. The phantoms varied in the number of tissue types and whether those tissues were modeled as homogeneous or heterogeneous. An SVM classifier was employed for the analysis. The best performance was achieved using the phantom composed of homogeneous fat and fibroglandular tissue, with an accuracy of 98.8%, sensitivity of 97.3%, specificity of 100%, *F1*-score of 99.0%, and a MCC of 0.98.

Vijayarveswari *et al* (2025) [116] investigated various FE and selection techniques for breast cancer detection using ML algorithms, including DT, probabilistic neural network (PNN), and NB. Three FE methods were evaluated: *K*-means, reconstruction ICA, and statistical FE. For feature selection, the methods tested were Relief-F, neighborhood component analysis (NCA), and particle swarm optimization. The dataset consisted of 2000 samples obtained from an experimental breast phantom, evenly divided between tumorous and non-tumorous cases. Among the extraction methods, statistical features performed best,

achieving an average accuracy of 75.05% across the three classifiers. When combined with NCA as the feature selection method, the system achieved an improved average accuracy of 85.03%, making Statistical Features + NCA the best-performing combination.

3.1.2. Deep learning

Woten *et al* (2007) [54] applied an ANN for breast cancer detection using a homogeneous breast numerical phantom containing a tumor. The dataset used in the study comprised 14 000 simulation cases: 4000 without tumor presence and 10 000 with tumor presence. The position of the tumor was varied across 100 random locations, and in both tumor and non-tumor (NT) cases, the electrical properties of the background were varied. The dataset was divided into training and test sets, each consisting of 7000 simulation cases. The ANN was trained and tested on these datasets under different noise conditions. Gaussian noise with a mean of zero and standard deviations of 0.001, 0.01, 0.1, 0.2, and 0.3 was added. The models were evaluated in two scenarios: one with binary classification (tumor present vs no tumor), where a single threshold of 0.5 was used to separate the two classes, and another with three-class classification (tumor present vs undecided vs no tumor), where a double threshold approach was applied, with cut-offs at 0.4 and 0.7: predictions below 0.4 were classified as 'no tumor', above 0.7 as 'tumor present', and those between 0.4 and 0.7 as 'undecided'. The best result for the binary classification, an accuracy of 97.59%, was achieved when the ANN was trained with noise of a standard deviation of 0.2. For the three-class classification, the best accuracy, 95.71%, was obtained with noise of standard deviation 0.1. Given the unbalanced dataset, additional performance metrics should be used to evaluate models performance, such as the *F1*-score or Matthew's CORR (MCC).

McGinley *et al* (2010) [64] proposed spiking neural network (SNN) as a tumor classification method. The SNN was employed along with a genetic algorithm (GA), with the parameters used for GA as detailed in [123]. In [64], the primary focus of the authors was the analysis of small tumors (up to 1 cm in radius). The tumor models used were based on the GRS model. A total of 368 tumor models were considered, comprising 184 of size 2.5 mm and 184 of size 7.5 mm. Among these tumors, 184 were of type 1 (malignant), 92 were of type 2 (macrolobulated benign), and 92 were of type 3 (smooth benign). The authors opted to employ LDA as a baseline for examining the performance and robustness of the SNN classifier. The dataset was randomly shuffled and divided into 75% for the training set and 25% for the test group. The algorithms were assessed using two types of classifier architectures: (i) a direct classifier that categorizes each tumor as either benign or malignant, and (ii) a two-stage classifier that initially categorizes each tumor as small or large, followed by categorization as benign or malignant. The results for the algorithms under the first classifier architecture showed an accuracy of 82.3% for LDA and 94.0% for SNN. For the two-stage classifier architecture, LDA demonstrated an accuracy of 91.2% for the size stage and 90.69% for the shape stage, while SNN exhibited 99.5% accuracy for the size stage and 98.71% for the shape stage.

Also using SNN, in O'Halloran *et al* (2011) [67], the authors introduced a new approach using the classifier within a three-dimensional breast model with varying dielectric properties, using the result of applying the DWT to the RTS. Their dataset consisted of simulated signals of 160 tumor models obtained through the GRS method, including 80 malignant, 40 macrolobulated benign, and 40 smooth benign cases. The researchers employed GA techniques to optimize the parameters of the SNN and compared its performance with a LDA classifier. Results indicated that the SNN outperformed the LDA classifier and showed resilience to increasing levels of model heterogeneity, achieving 98% of accuracy, 100% of sensitivity and 95.76% of specificity.

Yahya *et al* (2011) [68] implemented an ANN for breast cancer detection using a numerical breast phantom. The study considered tumors of three different sizes: 1 mm, 3 mm, and 5 mm. The dataset used to train and test the ANN comprised 1284 samples, with 1024 for training and 260 for testing. Each sample consisted of a feature vector obtained from the coefficients of a DWT. The paper did not disclose the class distribution or the number of samples corresponding to each tumor size. However, since the authors reported accuracy values for each tumor size separately, it is possible that 1284 samples were available for each tumor size. The highest classification accuracy was achieved for 5 mm tumors (100%), followed by 3 mm (76.56%) and 1 mm (65.52%).

Jones *et al* (2013) [71] employed self-organizing maps (SOMs) to effectively classify tumor models. These tumor models encompassed three categories: macrolobulated benign, and two types of MTs with different degrees of spiculation. In this study, 90 tumor models were used, consisting of 30 BTs and 60 MTs, with the malignant group further divided into 30 tumors with 3 spicules and 30 tumors with 10 spicules. Two distinct datasets were analyzed: one with data from simulations featuring a tumor located in homogeneous breast tissue, and the other set where the tumor was located in heterogeneous breast tissue. Each dataset comprised 360 tumor signals. To evaluate the classifier, each dataset was randomly shuffled and divided into ten combinations of 276 training and 84 testing tumors. The classification process was iterated 10 times for each combination, and the average performance of the classifier was calculated. The results indicated an accuracy

of 99.5% for macrolobulated BTs, 90.54% for 3 spiculated MTs, and 88.28% for 10 spiculated MTs, resulting in an overall average accuracy of 92.77%.

Caorsi *et al* (2017) [80] proposed a breast cancer detection approach using millimeter-wave signals and an ANN classifier. The authors employed four differentiated Gaussian pulses (DGP), each centered at a different frequency: 2 GHz, 6 GHz, 20 GHz, and 30 GHz. The dataset consisted of 200 samples, evenly split between Healthy (H) and Non-Healthy (NH) cases, and was divided equally into training and test sets (100 samples each). The best performance was achieved using data acquired with the 20 GHz DGP, where the ANN reached 92% accuracy, 96% sensitivity, and 88% specificity.

Hirose *et al* (2019) [86] proposed a neural network-based method for breast cancer detection using the raw electric field frequency response as input. The dataset comprised 1400 samples generated from numerical breast phantoms, equally divided between healthy and tumorous cases (700 each). The neural network achieved an accuracy of 86.7% in classifying the presence or absence of breast cancer.

Using the dataset from [121], Reimer *et al* (2022) [95] used a combined set of 1257 scans-1008 for training (augmented by a factor of 12) and 249 for testing-to evaluate CNN, DNN, and LR models. Among these, the CNN achieved the highest performance, with 75% accuracy, 82% sensitivity, and an AUC of 78%.

Eashour *et al* (2024) [105] used the 1008-scan dataset and implemented a paired-breast CNN strategy with data augmentation through horizontal flips and translations. The paired-breast CNN outperformed the single-breast model, achieving an AUC of 85%, 75% sensitivity, and 79% specificity.

To enhance model performance through data augmentation, Tariq *et al* (2025) [115] investigated the use of generative adversarial networks (GANs) to synthetically augment the first and second generations of the dataset. CNN models trained only on original data achieved 91.2% accuracy, 90.8% precision, 91.5% recall, and a 91.1% *F1*-score, whereas models trained solely on GAN-generated data showed slightly lower performance, with 89.7% accuracy, 89.1% precision, 90.2% recall, and an *F1*-score of 89.6%. However, combining original and synthetic data resulted in a marked improvement across all metrics, with 94.8% accuracy, 94.3% precision, 95.2% recall, and a 94.7% *F1*-score. The work by Tariq *et al* [115] highlights the potential of GAN-based data augmentation, which, when combined with real samples, led to significant gains in classification performance. The lowest performance was reported by Reimer *et al* [95], who trained models using a combination of the first and second generations.

Halim *et al* (2023) [99] employed a PNN for breast cancer detection using a dataset of 10 000 samples obtained from an experimental breast phantom. The class distribution was not disclosed. The dataset was split into a training set (60%) and a test set (40%). The authors evaluated five feature normalization techniques in both the time and frequency domains: binary normalization, decimal scaling, linear scaling, min-max, and *Z*-score. The highest performance was achieved using frequency-domain features normalized with *Z*-score, reaching an accuracy of 98.67%.

Lu *et al* (2023) [100] employed 1D CNN for breast cancer detection using backscattered signals generated from numerical breast phantoms. The dataset consisted of 5280 signals, evenly split between tumor-containing and healthy cases. The data were divided into a training set of 4224 signals and a test set of 1056 signals. The model achieved an accuracy of 98.20%, sensitivity of 96.52%, specificity of 100%, precision of 100%, and an *F1*-score of 98.23%. The authors also compared their results with previous studies by Liu *et al* [90] and Santorelli *et al* [74], showing that their 1D CNN approach outperformed these methods by more than 10 percentage points in terms of accuracy.

Ghosh *et al* (2024) [108] employed a CNN based on the AlexNet architecture to classify breast tumors. The model was evaluated on two classification tasks: (1) distinguishing between tumorous and non-tumorous cases, and (2) differentiating between benign and MTs. The dataset consisted of 1150 rMWI images of numerical breast phantoms without tumors, 1152 with BTs, and 1152 with MTs. For the tumor vs NT classification, it achieved 97.22% accuracy, 97.01% precision, 97.10% recall, and an *F1*-score of 97.12%. For the benign vs malignant classification, the model achieved an accuracy of 98.59%, precision of 98.40%, recall of 98.52%, and *F1*-score of 98.55%.

In Taghipour-Gorjikaie *et al* (2024) [109], using data acquired using the Mammowave device, an autoencoder decoder PNN (AEDPNN) was used, but performance was weak due to data unbalance, same data than [110], with 59.7% accuracy, 58.75% sensitivity, and 59.88% specificity.

Tables 8 compile information on the equipment configurations used for signal acquisition in microwave breast imaging studies. The reviewed works employed a diverse range of antenna setups, from single-element configurations to dense arrays with up to 144 positions. Most systems use monostatic or bistatic arrangements, although quasi-multistatic configurations also appear in several studies; in some cases, multiple arrangements are implemented within the same system. While fixed platforms remain predominant, many recent studies incorporate moving antenna systems to enhance spatial diversity. Operating frequencies span from sub-GHz levels to over 20 GHz, with the majority of studies focused within the 1–10 GHz range. A clear trend toward increased antenna counts and broader frequency coverage is

Table 8. Summary table on the equipment used for signal acquisition (Target zone: breast). Label ‘T’ represents transmitters, while ‘R’ represents receivers. When these labels are absent, the respective study did not distinguish between transmitters and receivers. The (*) indicates that the nomenclature used in this paper differs from that employed by the authors of the paper. ‘NA’ means not available.

Reference	No. of antenna positions	Monostatic vs multistatic	Moving vs fixed	Frequencies
Woten <i>et al</i> [54]	1 T 1 R	Bistatic	Fixed	6 GHz
Davies <i>et al</i> [57]	8	Monostatic	Fixed	6 GHz
Chen <i>et al</i> [58]	2 T 5 R	Multistatic	Fixed	1, 4 GHz
Chen <i>et al</i> [59]	2 T 5 R	Multistatic	Moving	1, 4 GHz
Chen <i>et al</i> [60]	1	Monostatic	Fixed	1 GHz
Teo <i>et al</i> [61]	5, 7	Monostatic	Fixed	6 GHz
Conceição <i>et al</i> [62]	4 T 4 R	Monostatic	Fixed	6 GHz
Kosmas <i>et al</i> [63]	7	Multistatic	Fixed	up to 10 GHz
McGinley <i>et al</i> [64]	4 T 4 R	Monostatic	Fixed	6 GHz
Conceição <i>et al</i> [65]	4 T 4 R	Monostatic	Fixed	6 GHz
Conceição <i>et al</i> [66]	4 T 4 R	Monostatic	Fixed	6 GHz
O’Halloran <i>et al</i> [67]	4 T 4 R	Monostatic	Fixed	6 GHz
Yahya <i>et al</i> [68]	24	Multistatic	Fixed	3.1–10.6 GHz
Byrne <i>et al</i> [69]	4 T 4 R	Multistatic	Fixed	6 GHz
Byrne <i>et al</i> [70]	4 T 4 R	Monostatic	Fixed	6 GHz
Jones <i>et al</i> [71]	4 T 4 R	Monostatic	Fixed	6 GHz
Santorelli <i>et al</i> [72]	16	Quasi-multistatic*	Fixed	2–4 GHz
Conceição <i>et al</i> [73]	144	Monostatic	Moving	1–6 GHz
Santorelli <i>et al</i> [74]	16	Quasi-multistatic*	Fixed	2–4 GHz
Reza <i>et al</i> [75]	1 T 1 R	Bistatic	Fixed	4.7 GHz
Conceição <i>et al</i> [76]	144	Monostatic	Moving	1–6 GHz
Li <i>et al</i> [77]	16	Quasi-multistatic*	Fixed	2–4 GHz
Sacristán <i>et al</i> [78]	NA	Multistatic	Moving	2.3–6.5 GHz
Gerazov <i>et al</i> [79]	4 T 4 R	Monostatic	Fixed	6 GHz
Caorsi <i>et al</i> [80]	NA	Monostatic	Fixed	20 GHz
Oliveira <i>et al</i> [81]	12	Multistatic	Fixed	6 GHz
Aydin <i>et al</i> [82]	1 T 1 R	Bistatic	Fixed	3–18 GHz
Aldhaeabi <i>et al</i> [83]	1	Monostatic	Fixed	916 MHz
Rana <i>et al</i> [84]	15 T 15 R	Bistatic	Moving	1–9 GHz
Reimer <i>et al</i> [85]	1 T 12 R	Bistatic	Moving	2.3–6.5 GHz
Hirose <i>et al</i> [86]	11 T 11 R	Multistatic	Fixed	0.207–4.14 GHz
Conceição <i>et al</i> [55]	144	Monostatic	Moving	1–6 GHz
Rana <i>et al</i> [87]	15 T 80 R	Multi-bistatic	Moving	1–9 GHz
Fasoula <i>et al</i> [88]	18	Multistatic	Fixed	0.5–4 GHz
Chen <i>et al</i> [89]	8	Multistatic	Fixed	3 GHz
Liu <i>et al</i> [90]	8	Quasi-Multistatic	Fixed	6 GHz
Sami <i>et al</i> [91]	72 T 72 R	Bistatic	Moving	2–4 GHz
Patel <i>et al</i> [92]	72 T 72 R	Monostatic/Bistatic	Moving	1–8 GHz
Martins <i>et al</i> [93]	1	Monostatic	Fixed	2–6 GHz
Janjic <i>et al</i> [94]	36 T 36 R	Bistatic	Moving	0.6–8 GHz
Reimer <i>et al</i> 2022 [95]	72	Monostatic/Bistatic	NA	1–8 GHz
Janjic <i>et al</i> [96]	36 T 36 R	Bistatic	Moving	1–8 GHz
Papini <i>et al</i> [97]	15 T 80 R	Bistatic*	Moving	1–9 GHz
Janjic <i>et al</i> [98]	NA	NA	NA	0.5–8 GHz
Halim <i>et al</i> [99]	2	Bistatic	Fixed	4.3 GHz
Lu <i>et al</i> [100]	12	Multistatic	Fixed	6 GHz
Ghavami <i>et al</i> [101]	15 T 80 R	Bistatic	Moving	1–9 GHz
Rana <i>et al</i> [102]	5 T 80 R	Bistatic	Moving	1–9 GHz
Abdelmawgood <i>et al</i> [103]	4	Quasi-multistatic	Fixed	3.5–5 GHz
Elnaggar <i>et al</i> [104]	4	Multistatic	Fixed	2.5–12 GHz
Eashour <i>et al</i> [105]	72 T 72 R	Multistatic	Moving	1–9 GHz
Shadwell <i>et al</i> [106]	2	Multi-bistatic	Moving	1–9 GHz

(Continued.)

Table 8. (Continued.)

Reference	No. of antenna positions	Monostatic vs multistatic	Moving vs fixed	Frequencies
Dridi <i>et al</i> [107]	NA	Monostatic/Bistatic	NA	1–8 GHz
Ghosh <i>et al</i> [108]	1	Monostatic	Fixed	2–10 GHz
Taghipour-Gorjikolaie <i>et al</i> [109]	8 T 8 R	Bistatic	Moving	1–9 GHz
Taghipour-Gorjikolaie <i>et al</i> [110]	10 T 80 R	Bistatic	Moving	1–9 GHz
Patil <i>et al</i> [111]	1	Monostatic	Fixed	2.76–11.14 GHz
Pelicano <i>et al</i> [112]	10	Monostatic	Fixed	3 GHz
Yurtseven <i>et al</i> [113]	36 T 36 R	Bistatic	Moving	0.6–8 GHz
Reimer <i>et al</i> [114]	NA	NA	NA	NA
Tariq <i>et al</i> [115]	72 T 72 R	Monostatic/Bistatic	Moving	1–8 GHz
Vijayarveswari <i>et al</i> [116]	2	Bistatic	Fixed	NA

evident in more recent contributions. However, inconsistencies in reporting practices and terminology, along with the limited adoption of standardized measurement setups, continue to pose challenges for direct comparison across studies.

The information regarding dataset sizes, input types, and model performance in the reviewed studies is summarized in table 9. These tables highlight a clear dominance of studies using feature vectors as model input, indicating widespread use of pre-processing techniques. Nevertheless, some studies use raw data directly from the acquisition devices, and in a few cases, images are used as input. The dataset sizes reported do not allow for conclusive analysis, as the number reported often refer to the number of raw measurements rather than the number of input samples actually used for training. Most studies employed balanced datasets, whereas the few that used unbalanced datasets often reported notably poorer performance. For instance, Taghipour-Gorjikolaie *et al* [109] used a highly unbalanced dataset-863 healthy and 161 unhealthy samples-and reported performance metrics around only 60%. Accuracy is the most commonly used evaluation metric; however, recent studies show a growing trend toward reporting multiple metrics, leading to a more robust and informative model evaluation.

3.2. Brain

The applications of combining ML and MWI to classify brain diseases included the classification of strokes, classification of various stages of AD, and the classification of brain tumors. Table 10 presents a summary of papers on the application of ML algorithms for classifying brain images using MWI.

3.2.1. ML

Salucci *et al* [124] pioneered the application of MWI for brain disease classification, specifically focusing on stroke detection using SVM. The authors trained SVM models on subsets of varying sizes ($N = 4$ to 2500) drawn from a dataset of 2500 samples, which comprised 50% stroke cases, equally divided between IS and ICH, and 50% healthy cases. All data were acquired using experimental phantoms. Model performance was evaluated using an independent test set of 500 samples. Since the model achieved 100% accuracy on the test set for training sizes equal to or greater than $N = 5$, only results up to that point were reported. While these results are promising, further validation using more complex phantoms and clinical data is necessary.

In a related study, Guo *et al* [125] proposed a new approach for stroke localization and classification using MWI. Their pipeline consisted of three main steps: (i) tomographic reconstruction of the brain's dielectric property profile using the BIM; (ii) FE via k -means clustering; and (iii) classification using an SVM model. Notably, the authors did not include healthy subjects in their analysis, assuming stroke diagnosis had already been made. They employed two MRI-derived numerical phantoms: Phantom A ($256 \times 256 \times 128$ voxels) and Phantom B (256×256 pixels). Classification was posed as a binary task distinguishing ICH from IS. Both training and testing datasets included 600 BIM-generated images (200 per SNR-level: 40 dB, 25 dB, 10 dB), with 100 images per class and SNR level. The SVM achieved 93.5% accuracy in low-noise conditions (40 dB) and over 81% accuracy in high-noise conditions (10 dB). When combining all SNR levels, the framework attained an 88% overall classification accuracy, demonstrating its robustness.

Building upon this line of research, Zhu *et al* [56] introduced a novel method using graph degree mutual information (GDMI) to differentiate directly between ICH and IS from electromagnetic signals. They simulated 100 realistic brain models using segmented MRI data and an antenna array operating from 0.7 to 2 GHz. The time-domain signals were obtained via inverse Fast Fourier Transform, resulting in 16×16 time series per model. These were converted into graphs using the fast weighted horizontal visibility algorithm, with features extracted using GDMI and classified using an SVM. Using 50 ICH and 50 IS samples, the

Table 9. Summary of dataset characteristics and evaluation metrics.

Reference	Dataset	Class balance	Input sample	Metric
Woten <i>et al</i> [54]	14 000 (Signal)	4000/10 000 (H/NH)	Signal	Acc: 97.59%
Davies <i>et al</i> [57]	90 (TM)	30/30/30 (S/micro/Sp)	FV	Acc:99.40%
Chen <i>et al</i> [58]	60 (TM)	30/30 (Macro/micro)	Signals	ROC: NA
Chen <i>et al</i> [59]	60 (TM)	30/30 (Macro/micro)	Signals	ROC: NA
Chen <i>et al</i> [60]	60 (TM)	30/30 (Macro/micro)	Signals	ROC: NA
Teo <i>et al</i> [61]	60 (TM)	30/30(S/Sp)	Signals	NA
Conceição <i>et al</i> [62]	352 (TM)	NA	FV	Acc: 85.99%
Kosmas <i>et al</i> [63]	NA (TM)	NA (Macro/Micro)	Signals	NA
McGinley <i>et al</i> [64]	368 (TM)	184/92/92 (Mal/MaB/SB)	FV	Acc: 98.71%
Conceição <i>et al</i> [65]	352 (TM)	176/176 (Ben/Mal)	FV	Acc: 87.05%
Conceição <i>et al</i> [66]	480 (TM)	NA	FV	Acc: 92.71%, 73.96%
O'Halloran <i>et al</i> [67]	160 (TM)	80/40/40 (Mal/MaB/SB)	FV	Acc, Sen, Spe: 98%, 100%, 95.76%
Yahya <i>et al</i> [68]	1284 (FV)	NA	FV	Acc (5 mm, 3 mm, 1 mm): 100%, 76.56%, 65.52%
Byrne <i>et al</i> [69]	1728 (FV)	NA	FV	Acc: 83.66%
Byrne <i>et al</i> [70]	2880 (Signals)	1440/1440 (H/NH)	FV	Acc: 94.95%
Jones <i>et al</i> [71]	90 (TM)	NA	FV	92.77%
Santorelli <i>et al</i> [72]	230 (Breast scans)	115/115 (H/NH)	FV	Acc: 73.64%
Conceição <i>et al</i> [73]	26 (TM)	13/13 (Ben/Mal)	FV	Acc: 89.34%
Santorelli <i>et al</i> [74]	320	50%/50% (H/NH)	FV	Acc, FP, FN: 77,53%, 8.33%, 37.41%
Reza <i>et al</i> [75]	300	36/264 (H/NH)	FV	Acc, Sen, Spe: 100%, 100%, 100%
Conceição <i>et al</i> [76]	26 (TM)	13/13 (Ben/Mal)	FV	Acc: 90.95%
Li <i>et al</i> [77]	290 (Phantoms)	150/140 (H/NH)	FV	AGE: 0.129
Sacristán <i>et al</i> [78]	1534/2395 (Breast models)	50%/50% (H/NH)	FV	Acc: 94%, 62%
Gerazov <i>et al</i> [79]	240 (TM)	80/160 (Ben/Mal)	FV	Acc: 92.81%
Caorsi <i>et al</i> [80]	200 (NA)	100/100 (H/NH)	FV	Acc, Sen, Spe: 92%, 96%, 88%
Oliveira <i>et al</i> [81]	84 240 (FV)	NA	FV	ROC: NA
Aydin <i>et al</i> [82]	400 (signals)	NA	FV	Acc: 94%
Aldhaeabi <i>et al</i> [83]	90 (Breast model)	45/45 (H/NH)	FV	Acc, Rec, Spe, Prec: 65%, 55%, 75%, 68.8%
Rana <i>et al</i> [84]	23 (Breasts)	12/11 (H/NH)	NA	Acc, Sen, Spe: 98.9%, 97.7%, 99.7% NA
Reimer <i>et al</i> [85]	2000/2001 (Phantoms)	50%/50% (H/Mal)	FV	Sen, Spe, AUC: 83%, 91%; 94%
Hirose <i>et al</i> [86]	1400 (NA)	700/700 (H/NH)	Scattered field	Acc: 85%
Conceição <i>et al</i> [55]	26 (TM)	13/13 (Ben/Mal)	FV	Acc: 96.2%, 92.3%
Rana <i>et al</i> [87]	61 (Breast exams)	25/36 (H/NH)	FV	Acc, Sen, Spe: 91%, 84.40%, 97.20%
Fasoula <i>et al</i> [88]	24 (Patients)	11/8/5 (BPBC/UC/BPBBL)	Solidity, Correlation, Busyness	CL: 11.50%
Chen <i>et al</i> [89]	600 (Signal)	NA	Signal	Acc, F1: 72.5%, 72.8%
Liu <i>et al</i> [90]	11 232 (Signals)	5616/5616 (H/NH)	FV	Acc: 84.8%
Sami <i>et al</i> [91]	1008 (Matrix S_{21})	NA	Signal	Acc, Sen, Spe: 99.7%, 99.2%, 99.9%
Patel <i>et al</i> [92]	249 (Breast Scans)	NA	FV	Acc, Sen, Spe, AUC: 94%, 100%, 89.2%, 94%
Martins <i>et al</i> [93]	480 (Breast scans)	240/240 (H/NH)	FV	Acc: 80%
Janjic <i>et al</i> [94]	54 (Breast exams)	29/25 (Ben/Mal)	S_{ij} Matrix	Acc, Sen, Spe: 81%, 80%, 83%
Reimer <i>et al</i> [95]	1257 (Breast scans)	NA	Matrix S_{11}	Acc, Sen, Spe, AUC: 75%, 82%, 70%, 78%
Janjic <i>et al</i> [96]	113 (Breast exams)	70/43 (Ben/Mal)	S_{ij} Matrix	Acc, Sen, Spe: 78%, 79%, 77%

(Continued.)

Table 9. (Continued.)

Reference	Dataset	Class balance	Input sample	Metric
Papini <i>et al</i> [97]	697 (Breast exams)	574/123 (H/NH)	Signals/FV	Acc, Sen, Spe: 88%, 86%, 89% 83%, 77%, 85%
Janjic <i>et al</i> [98]	558 (Breast scans)	390/168 (H/NH)	Signal	Acc, Sen, Spe: 93%, 95%, 92%
Halim <i>et al</i> [99]	10 000 (FV)	NA	FV	Acc: 98.67%
Lu <i>et al</i> [100]	5280 (Signal)	NA	Signal	Acc, Sen, Spe, Prec, F1: 98.20%, 96.52%, 100%, 100%, 98.23%
Ghavami <i>et al</i> [101]	697 (Breast scans)	321/376 (Ben/Mal)	FV	Acc, Sen, Spe: 90%, 90%, 92%
Rana <i>et al</i> [102]	61 (Breasts)	26/35 (Ben/Mal)	FV	Acc, Sen, Spe: 91%, 84%, 95%
Abdelmawgood <i>et al</i> [103]	1001 (Signal)	50%/50% (H/NH)	FV	Acc: 98.5%
Elnaggar <i>et al</i> [104]	1602/2403 (FV)	801/801; 801/801/801 (H/NH; H/1 T/2 T)	FV	Acc, Rec, Prec, F1: 98%, 98%, 98%, 99%, 98.67%, 98.67%, 98.67%
Eashour <i>et al</i> [105]	4030 (Images)	NA	Images	Sen, Spe, AUC: 75%, 79%, 85%
Shadwell <i>et al</i> [106]	352	120/170/62 (H/Ben/Mal)	FV	Acc: 80%
Dridi <i>et al</i> [107]	249 (Breast scans)	NA	FV	Acc, Sen, Spe: 98%, 96.15%, 100%
Ghosh <i>et al</i> [108]	3454/2304 (Images)	1150/2304 (H, NT); 1152/1152 (Ben, Mal)	Images	Acc, Rec, Prec, F1: 97.22%, 97.10%, 97.01%, 97.12%; 98.59%, 98.52%, 98.40%, 98.55%
Taghipour-Gorjikotaie <i>et al</i> [109]	1026 (Breast scans)	863/161 (H/NH)	FV	Acc, Sen, Spe: 59.70%, 58.75%, 59.88%
Taghipour-Gorjikotaie <i>et al</i> [110]	1026 (Breast scans)	863/161 (H/NH)	FV	Acc, Sen, Spe: 64.49%, 61.25%, 65.08%
Patil <i>et al</i> [111]	804 (FV)	NA	FV	Acc, Sen, Spe, Prec, F1, AUC: 98.04%, 96.72%, 96.67%, 96.72%, 96.72%, 98.05%
Pelicano <i>et al</i> [112]	830 (Observations)	460/370 (Ben/Mal)	FV	Acc, Sen, Spe, F1, MCC: 98.8%, 97.3%, 100%, 99.0%, 0.98
Yurtseven <i>et al</i> [113]	526 (Patients)	286/240 (Ben+H/Mal)	Matrices S_{11} and S_{12}	Acc, Sen, Spe: 91%, 91%, 92%
Reimer <i>et al</i> [114]	200 (Breast Scans)	NA	FV	AUC: NA
Tariq <i>et al</i> [115]	1257 (Breast Scans)	NA	Spectrograms	Acc, Rec, Prec, F1: 94.8%, 95.2%, 94.3%, 94.7%
Vijayasarveswari <i>et al</i> [116]	2000 (data samples)	1000/1000 (H/NH)	FV	Acc: 85.03%

1 Tumor (1 T), 2 Tumor (2 T), accuracy (Acc), average generalization error (AGE), benign (Ben), biopsy-proven benign breast lesions (BPBBL), biopsy-proven breast cancer (BPBC), false negative rate (FN), false positive rate (FP), feature vector (FV), healthy (H), macrolobulated (Macro), macrolobulated Benign (MaB), Malignant (Mal), Matthew's correlation coefficient (MCC), microlobulated (Micro), not available (NA), Not Healthy (NH), precision (Prec), recall (Rec), receiver operating characteristic (ROC), sensitivity (Sen), Smooth (S), smooth benign (SB), specificity (Spe), spiculated (Sp), tumor models (TM), unspirated cysts (UC).

method achieved 91% sensitivity, 98% specificity, and 94% accuracy in noiseless conditions. Under noise levels of 40 dB, 25 dB, and 10 dB, accuracies dropped to 93%, 88%, and 77%, respectively, with an overall accuracy of 89%. These results align with those of Guo *et al* [125], confirming that noise degrades classification performance, although Guo *et al*'s method maintained a slight accuracy advantage.

Complementing these earlier efforts, Pokorny *et al* [130] have conducted a series of studies applying SVM to classify brain strokes using MWI data derived from numerical head models. The authors investigated multi-class classification using SVMs with data from numerical head models. They introduced a new class-no stroke (noStroke)-resulting in a three-class problem: IS, ICH, and noStroke. They used head models from the IT²IS Foundation, to create three datasets: (1) 1000 simulations per class with predefined stroke sizes and positions; (2) 200 simulations per class with random sizes and fixed positions; and (3) 200 simulations per class with both random sizes and positions. Four hypotheses regarding generalization from

Table 10. Classification using machine learning models (Target zone: brain).

Reference	Algorithm	Type of Data
Salucci <i>et al</i> [124]	SVM	Numerical
Guo <i>et al</i> [125]	SVM	Numerical
Zhu <i>et al</i> [56]	SVM	Numerical
Saied <i>et al</i> [126]	LR, LDA, KNN, DT, NB, SVM	Numerical
Hossain <i>et al</i> [127]	YOLOv5	Experimental
Lalitha <i>et al</i> [128]	SVM, KNN, Bagging, RF, J48, NB, DT	Numerical
Hossain <i>et al</i> [129]	MBINet	Experimental
Pokorny <i>et al</i> [130]	SVM	Numerical
Pokorny <i>et al</i> [131]	SVM	Numerical
Ullah <i>et al</i> [132]	KNN RF DT	Numerical
Hossain <i>et al</i> [133]	MSegNet, BINet	Experimental
Cardinali <i>et al</i> [134]	MLP	Experimental
Taha <i>et al</i> [135]	BrainVisionNet	Experimental
Hasan <i>et al</i> [136]	SVM, KNN, RF, ANN	Numerical
Hasan <i>et al</i> [137]	RF, SVM, XGBoost	Numerical
Hashir <i>et al</i> [138]	TinyML	Numerical
Cardinali <i>et al</i> [139]	SVM	Experimental
Hossain <i>et al</i> [140]	FT-FEDTL	Experimental
Hasan <i>et al</i> [141]	CNN	Clinical
Pokorny <i>et al</i> [142]	SVM	Numerical
Lalitha <i>et al</i> [143]	YOLOv5l	Numerical
Farhatullah <i>et al</i> [144]	CNN	Numerical
Sudhakaran <i>et al</i> [145]	MobileNet v2	Experimental
Sudhakaran <i>et al</i> [146]	Hybrid Inception-CNN	Experimental
Yuan <i>et al</i> [147]	ANN	Clinical

Artificial neural network (ANN), BrainImageNet (BINet), convolutional neural network (CNN), decision tree (DT), fine-tuned feature-extracted deep transfer learning (FT-FEDTL), k-nearest neighbors (KNN), linear discriminant analysis (LDA), logistic regression (LR), microwave brain image network (MBINet), MicrowaveSegNet (MSegNet), multi-layer perceptron (MLP), Naïve Bayes (NB), random forest (RF), support vector machines (SVM).

small stroke data were tested. When trained on small stroke data, SVMs achieved 95.7% accuracy on similar stroke sizes but only 65.5% on larger strokes. Surprisingly, using multi-frequency data led to worse results (33.3% accuracy with 25 frequencies) than single-frequency input (94.6%), but PCA-based dimensionality reduction improved performance across all cases (up to 96.9%). For strokes with randomized size and position, accuracy dropped to a maximum of 70.5%, indicating that training data diversity and input dimensionality significantly affect model robustness.

In another study, Pokorny *et al* [131] used 2D datasets for multi-class classification and compared SVM with other classifiers, including LR, discriminant analysis, KNN, NB, and DT. They employed Bayesian optimization for hyperparameter tuning and found that increasing the separation between adjacent antennas improved performance—accuracy rose from 66.2% to 68.7% and Cohen’s kappa from 0.24 to 0.29. Though the overall accuracy was lower than in their previous 3D study, the work provided insight into how antenna configuration impacts classification outcomes.

In 2024, Pokorny *et al* [142] presented a systematic evaluation of SVM performance in both binary and three-class classification. Two datasets were used: 3D_2 for training (600 samples across noStroke, IS, and ICH), and 3D_3 for testing (300 samples). In the binary case (noStroke vs IS), SVM achieved 86.7% accuracy. In the three-class model, it reached 86.3%. These findings underscore the effectiveness of SVM for MWI-based stroke classification, particularly when class balance and training data quality are well controlled.

The first study of AD using MWI data was presented by Saied *et al* (2021) [126]. They used five ML algorithms, namely LR, KNN, DT, NB, and SVM, with the aim of classifying various stages of AD using data obtained from numerical model simulations. Additionally, LDA was used in their study. These models were developed in the CST Microwave Studio Suite, with measurements acquired from previous studies [148, 149]. Each stage of AD (normal, Mild AD, Moderate AD, and Severe AD) was represented by changes in the dielectric properties of specific regions and tissues. Simulations were conducted using six antennas, and the signals from each antenna were aggregated into a single dataset for each simulation case. This dataset was then divided into a training set, comprising approximately 78% of the complete simulation cases, and a validation set, which accounted for the remaining 22%. The results of the study indicated that LR achieved

the highest estimated average accuracy score, reaching 98.97%, while LDA exhibited an estimated average accuracy of 95.56%. However, the other algorithms displayed accuracy levels below 80%.

Another study in the field of neurological diseases was conducted by Ullah *et al* in 2023 [132], where the authors proposed a ML-based classification method using KNN, RFs, and classification and regression tree (CART) for the early diagnosis of acute neurological conditions, focusing on AD. The data used in this study were obtained through simulations performed on realistic numerical brain phantoms using the CST Studio Suite to capture the scattered signals. These head models comprised various tissue layers, including the skull, skin, blood, white matter, and gray matter. The models represented three states of AD: normal, mild AD, and severe AD. After data preprocessing, the authors obtained a dataset of 3600 samples. The results of this study yielded accuracies of 79.0%, 83.2%, and 81.0% for the KNN, RF, and CART algorithms, respectively. The authors concluded that the proposed ML-based classification method, coupled with MWI algorithms, could potentially be used to monitor AD at its early stages. They intend to evaluate the proposed method on more realistic data obtained from AD patients in future studies. Comparing these results with those presented in [126], it is evident that the latter achieved superior performance. Specifically, the best-performing model in that study was LR with an accuracy of 98.97%.

While the previous studies relied exclusively on simulation data, Cardinali *et al* (2024) [139] trained and tested SVM models on the four datasets. The best results were achieved with Dataset 2, which included 890 measurements-290 healthy and 600 AD cases. The SVM achieved 95.7% accuracy, outperforming the MLP model from the previous study.

Lalitha *et al* (2022) [128] evaluated the performance of several ML algorithms for brain cancer detection, including Bagging, KNN, RF, J48, SVM, NB, and CARTs. Although the dataset size was not disclosed, the models were evaluated using 10-fold cross-validation. Among the algorithms tested, RF achieved the highest average accuracy at 92.01%.

Hasan *et al* (2023) [136] compared the performance of SVM, KNN, RF, and ANN for brain cancer detection. Three datasets were used: Dataset S, in which each sample contained acquisition frequency and scattering parameters; Dataset Y, comprising frequency and admittance parameters; and Dataset Z, consisting of frequency and impedance parameters. Each dataset contained 2002 samples generated from a numerical head phantom. The class distribution (healthy vs tumorous) was not disclosed. ANN models outperformed the other algorithms across all datasets, achieving the best performance on Dataset Z with 99.60% accuracy, 99.70% sensitivity, 100% specificity, and an AUC of 100%. Subsequently, Hasan *et al* (2023) [137] extended the analysis by including a fourth dataset, SYZ, in which each sample combined frequency with scattering, admittance, and impedance parameters. The models tested in this follow-up study were RF, SVM, and XGBoost. All four datasets contained 2002 samples, with class distribution again not reported. The best results were achieved with Dataset SYZ, where XGBoost attained 98.25% accuracy, 96.68% sensitivity, 100% specificity, and an AUC of 100%.

3.2.2. Deep learning

Moving beyond traditional SVM-based approaches, Hashir *et al* [138] proposed a portable MWI system for stroke detection based on TinyML and compressed deep learning models. Data augmentation increased the dataset size from 300 to 1240 scans. Two lightweight model variants were tested (pruned and quantized), with the pruned model achieving the best results: 93% accuracy and a 92.9% *F1*-score.

Focusing on deep learning techniques, Hasan *et al* [141] introduced a wavelet-based CNN for classifying IS and ICH. Using 941 samples (458 IS, 483 ICH), they trained on 752 and tested on 189. Various input types were evaluated, including complex S-parameters, time-domain signals, continuous wavelet transform (CWT), and scaled CWT. The best results came from scaled CWT fed into a 2D CNN, which achieved 84.38% accuracy, 87.10% recall, 84.85% precision, and 85.08% *F1*-score.

Finally, Yuan *et al* [147] proposed a deep learning framework combining MWI system configuration, signal-derived features, and clinical variables. The dataset included 431 subjects (196 healthy, 235 stroke). Subjects were split into training (235), validation (49), and test (147) sets. The model that used all three input types achieved the best result with 76.19% accuracy, demonstrating the value of multi-modal integration in stroke classification.

Cardinali *et al* (2023) [134] was the first study on AD detection using a DL approach, proposing the use of a MLP for it. The same four datasets from [139] were used. The best results were obtained with Dataset 4, which contained 860 samples-260 from healthy individuals and 600 from individuals with AD. The MLP achieved an accuracy of 90.8%.

More recently, Farhatullah *et al* (2025) [144] implemented deep learning models combining CNN with long short-term memory (LSTM), gated recurrent units (GRUs), and bidirectional LSTM architectures for AD classification. The dataset consisted of 162 signals, evenly distributed among three classes: healthy, mild AD, and severe AD. Although data augmentation techniques were applied, the final dataset size was not disclosed. The data were split into a training set (70%) and a test set (30%). The best performance was achieved using the CNN + GRU model, which attained 87% accuracy, 87% precision, 87% recall, and 87% *F1*-score. This model also outperformed those proposed by Ullah *et al* (2023) [132].

Hossain *et al* have conducted a series of studies exploring the use of rMWI reconstructed brain images and deep learning models for multi-class brain tumor classification. In their 2022 study [127], they proposed three YOLOv5 variants-YOLOv5s, YOLOv5m, and YOLOv5l-for classifying six tumor types: NT, BT, MT, double BT (DBT), double MT (DMT), and benign-malignant combination (BMT). Data augmentation expanded the initial 400 images to 4400, with YOLOv5l achieving the best performance: 96.32% accuracy, 94.98% recall, 95.17% precision, 95.28% specificity, and a 95.53% *F1*-score. In 2023, they introduced MBINet [129], an eight-layer lightweight classifier based on a self-organized operational neural network, applied to a dataset of 1320 reconstructed images, augmented to 13 200. Using five-fold cross-validation, MBINet achieved 96.97% accuracy and outperformed conventional CNNs and pre-trained models such as ResNet and DenseNet. In another 2023 study [133], the authors proposed MicrowaveSegNet for segmentation and BrainImageNet for classification, using a dataset initially composed of 300 reconstructed images and augmented to 6000. Classification accuracy reached 89.33% with raw images and 98.33% with segmented images, demonstrating the effectiveness of integrating segmentation into the pipeline. Most recently, Hossain *et al* (2024) [140] presented the FT-FEDTL model, a fine-tuned deep transfer learning approach tested on an expanded and augmented version of their previous dataset. FT-FEDTL achieved better results with both unbalanced and balanced dataset. With the unbalanced dataset, it reached 96.25% accuracy, 96.15% precision, 96.05% recall, 95.28% specificity, and a 96.04% *F1*-score. With the balanced dataset, it achieved remarkable results: 99.65% accuracy, 99.48% precision, 99.16% recall, 99.10% specificity, and a 99.23% *F1*-score. These outcomes demonstrate consistent improvements over prior models and highlight the growing robustness and accuracy of deep learning techniques applied to reconstructed brain image classification.

Lalitha *et al* (2024) [143] implemented the YOLOv5l algorithm to classify brain tumors as malignant or benign using reconstructed images. The dataset consisted of 500 reconstructed images, split into 350 for training, 75 for validation, and 75 for testing. Data augmentation was applied to the training set, increasing it to 1000 images. The YOLOv5l model achieved 92.32% accuracy, 90.3% precision, and 91.5% *F1*-score.

Taha *et al* (2023) [135] developed and evaluated BrainVisionNet, a deep learning model for brain tumor classification using rMWI reconstructed images. The original dataset consisted of 310 reconstructed images, which was expanded to 5000 images through data augmentation. The final dataset included 1798 images without tumors, 1648 with one tumor, and 1554 with two tumors. The data were divided into a training set of 4000 images and a test set of 1000 images. BrainVisionNet was evaluated using accuracy, precision, recall, and *F1*-score, achieving 99.2%, 99.3%, 99.3%, and 99.0%, respectively. These results outperformed prior studies using similar methodologies, including the work of Hossain *et al* (2023) [133].

Finally, Sudhakaran *et al* (2025) [145] implemented the MobileNet V2 architecture for brain tumor detection using rMWI reconstructed images. The dataset consisted of 1282 reconstructed brain images, with 672 labeled as tumorous and 610 as healthy. The data were split into a training set of 1026 images and a test set of 256 images. Although data augmentation techniques were applied, it was not specified whether the dataset description referred to pre- or post-augmentation values. The model's performance was compared with six other studies-five using MRI data and one using microwave imaging [129]. MobileNet V2 outperformed all previous models, achieving 98.44% accuracy, 98.03% precision, 99.00% recall, 97.82% specificity, and 98.52% *F1*-score. In a separate study, Sudhakaran *et al* (2025) [146] applied a Hybrid Inception-CNN (HI-CNN) to the same dataset. Performance was again compared with models from the literature, including two microwave-based approaches [127, 129] and others using MRI or CT data. The HI-CNN outperformed all compared models, achieving 99.48% accuracy, 99% precision, 100% recall, 100% specificity, and 99.50% *F1*-score. To note, the reported metrics suggest a potential inconsistency, as achieving both 100% recall and 100% specificity should imply an accuracy of 100%, which was not observed.

Table 11 summarizes information on the devices used in the reviewed studies for brain MWI classification. The number of antenna positions used for signal acquisition ranged from 4 to 50, for both transmission and reception, with most systems clustering at either end of this spectrum. A majority of the devices (22 out of 25) employed a multistatic configuration, while only two used monostatic setups and one

Table 11. Summary table on the equipment used for signal acquisition (Target zone: brain). Label ‘T’ represents transmitters, while ‘R’ represents receivers. When these labels are absent, the respective study did not distinguish between transmitters and receivers.

Reference	No. of antenna positions	Monostatic vs multistatic	Moving vs fixed	Frequencies
Salucci <i>et al</i> [124]	8	Multistatic	Fixed	900 MHz
Guo <i>et al</i> [125]	36	Multistatic	Fixed	0.85 GHz
Zhu <i>et al</i> [56]	16	Multistatic	Fixed	0.7–2 GHz
Saied <i>et al</i> [126]	6	Monostatic	Fixed	0.2–3 GHz
Hossain <i>et al</i> [127]	50 T 50 R	Multistatic	Moving	1–4 GHz
Lalitha <i>et al</i> [128]	2	Bistatic	Moving	3.2–4.5 GHz
Hossain <i>et al</i> [129]	50 T 50 R	Multistatic	Moving	1–4 GHz
Pokorny <i>et al</i> [130]	10	Multistatic	Fixed	0.8–2 GHz
Pokorny <i>et al</i> [131]	10	Multistatic	Fixed	1 GHz
Ullah <i>et al</i> [132]	6	Multistatic	Fixed	0.20–3 GHz
Hossain <i>et al</i> [133]	50 T 50 R	Multistatic	Moving	1–4 GHz
Cardinali <i>et al</i> [134]	4	Multistatic	Fixed	0.5–6.5 GHz
Taha <i>et al</i> [135]	50 T 50 R	Multistatic	Moving	1–4 GHz
Hasan <i>et al</i> [136]	4	Multistatic	Fixed	3.1–10.6 GHz
Hasan <i>et al</i> [137]	4	Multistatic	Fixed	3.1–10.6 GHz
Hashir <i>et al</i> [138]	45 T 45 R	Monostatic	Moving	2–4 GHz
Cardinali <i>et al</i> [139]	4	Multistatic	Fixed	0.5–6.5 GHz
Hossain <i>et al</i> [140]	50 T 50 R	Multistatic	Moving	1–4 GHz
Hasan <i>et al</i> [141]	16	Multistatic	Fixed	0.5–2 GHz
Pokorny <i>et al</i> [142]	10	Multistatic	Fixed	1 GHz
Lalitha <i>et al</i> [143]	9	Multistatic	Fixed	3 GHz
Farhatullah <i>et al</i> [144]	6	Multistatic	Fixed	0.20–3 GHz
Sudhakaran <i>et al</i> [145]	50 T 50 R	Multistatic	Moving	3.7 and 6.7 GHz
Sudhakaran <i>et al</i> [146]	50 T 50 R	Multistatic	Moving	3.7 and 6.7 GHz
Yuan <i>et al</i> [147]	20	Multistatic	Fixed	1–10 GHz

used a bistatic arrangement. No consistent trend was observed regarding whether the antennas were fixed or movable, although fixed configurations were more commonly reported. Operating frequencies ranged from 200 MHz to 10.6 GHz, with rMWI systems being more prevalent.

Information on the datasets, dataset balance, input types, and model performance from the reviewed brain classification studies is summarized in table 12. In contrast to breast classification, the most common input in brain studies is reconstructed images. Overall, this input has led to the best model performances, with studies using reconstructed images typically reporting evaluation metrics close to or exceeding 95%. Accuracy remains the most frequently used metric; however, the trend towards reporting multiple evaluation metrics, enhances the reliability of performance assessments. This shift may be partly explained by the fact that brain classification studies are relatively more recent than those focused on breast classification, with the earliest reviewed work in brain classification published in 2017 [124].

4. Discussion

The scoping review conducted in this article underscores the potential of combining MWI and ML, highlighting the variety of applications this combination offers. These applications range from breast disease detection to strokes, leg imaging, and brain diseases such as AD. MWI provides less invasive, faster, and more comfortable options for patients. For instance, in breast cancer detection, traditional imaging methods can cause discomfort due to breast compression. Additionally, these systems have the potential to be low-cost, as shown by Li *et al* (2015) [77], and more portable, thereby increasing accessibility to certain types of medical examinations.

Over time, there has been an evident increase on the sophistication of the algorithms used. Early studies relied on classical ML models such as SVM and KNN. However, more recent studies have employed either improved versions of these algorithms, such as the enhanced SVM in Li *et al* (2015) [77], or DL algorithms, such as CNNs, as presented by Mojabi *et al* (2021) [23]. In addition, innovative approaches, such as the one presented by Hossain *et al* (2023) [133], show promising results. Among the reviewed reconstruction studies, CNN and U-Net architectures are the most frequently adopted and show the most promising results, while SVMs remain the predominant and best-performing algorithms for classification. These reflect the broader trend of DL methods excelling in complex image reconstruction and SVMs in classification tasks.

Table 12. Summary of dataset characteristics and evaluation metrics.

Reference	Dataset	Class Balance	Input Sample	Metric
Salucci <i>et al</i> [124]	50 (Samples)	25/25 (H/NH)	NA	Acc: 100%
Guo <i>et al</i> [125]	1200 (BIM-generated images)	50/50 (ICH/IS)	FV	Acc: 88%
Zhu <i>et al</i> [56]	25 600 (Time Series Signals)	50/50 (ICH/IS)	Time Series Signals	Acc, Sen, Spe: 94%, 91%, 96%
Saied <i>et al</i> [126]	36 (Simulation Cases)	9/9/9/9 (H/MiAD/MoAD/SAD)	Signal	Acc: 98.97%
Hossain <i>et al</i> [127]	4400 (Images)	1100/3300 (H/NH)	Images	Acc, Rec, Spe, Prec, F1: 96.32%, 94.98%, 95.28%, 95.17%, 95.53%
Lalitha <i>et al</i> [128]	NA	NA	FV	Acc: 92.01%
Hossain <i>et al</i> [129]	13 677 (Images)	3108/2228/2228/2072/2072/1969 (H/BT/MT/DBT/DMT/BMT)	Images	Acc, Rec, Spe, Prec, F1: 96.97%, 96.85%, 97.95%, 96.93%, 96.83%
Pokorny <i>et al</i> [130]	3600, 3600, 1200 (S_{ij} Matrix)	(20% per size), (uniform density), (uniform density)	S_{ij} Matrix	Acc: 95.7%, 96.9%, 70.2%
Pokorny <i>et al</i> [131]	NA	NA	FV	Acc: 68.7%
Ullah <i>et al</i> [132]	3600 (Signal)	1200/1200/1200 (H, MiAD, SAD)	Signal	Acc: 83.2%
Hossain <i>et al</i> [133]	6108 (Images)	2016/2044/2048 (H, 1 T, 2 T)	Images	Acc, Rec, Spe, Prec, F1: 89.33%, 88.67%, 94.33%, 88.74%, 88.61%
Cardinali <i>et al</i> [134]	1690 (Signals)	570/1120 (H/NH)	Signal	Acc: 90.8%
Taha <i>et al</i> [135]	5000 (Images)	1798/1554/1648 (H/1 T/2 T)	Images	Acc, Rec, Prec, F1: 99.2%, 99.3%, 99.3%, 99.0%
Hasan <i>et al</i> [136]	2002 (FV)	NA	FV	Acc, Sen, Spe, AUC: 99.60%, 99.70%, 100%, 100%
Hasan <i>et al</i> [137]	2002 (FV)	NA	FV	Acc, Sen, Spe, AUC: 98.25%, 96.68%, 100%, 100%
Hashir <i>et al</i> [138]	1240 (Images)	NA	Images	Acc, F1: 93%, 92.9%
Cardinali <i>et al</i> [139]	1690 (Signals)	570/1120 (H/NH)	NA	Acc: 95.7%
Hossain <i>et al</i> [140]	4200 (Images)	700/700/700/700/700/700 (H/BT/MT/DBT/DMT/BMT)	Images	Acc, Rec, Spe, Prec, F1: 99.65%, 99.48%, 99.16%, 99.10%, 99.23%
Hasan <i>et al</i> [141]	941 (Scans)	483/458 (ICH/IS)	Scalograms	Acc, Rec, Prec, F1: 84.38%, 87.10%, 84.85%, 85.08%
Pokorny <i>et al</i> [142]	600/900 (Measurements)	300/300 (H/IS); 300/300/300 (H/IS/ICH)	S_{ij} Matrix	Acc: 86.7%, 86.3%
Lalitha <i>et al</i> [143]	1000 (Images)	NA	Images	Acc, Prec, F1: 92.32%, 90.3%, 91.5%
Farhatullah <i>et al</i> [144]	162 (Signal)	54/54/54 (H, MiAD, SAD)	Signal	Acc, Rec, Prec, F1: 87%, 87%, 87%, 87%

(Continued.)

Table 12. (Continued.)

Reference	Dataset	Class Balance	Input Sample	Metric
Sudhakaran <i>et al</i> [145]	1282 (Images)	610/672 (H/NH)	RMW Images	Acc, Rec, Spe, Prec, F1: 98.44%, 99.00%, 97.82%, 98.03%, 98.52%
Sudhakaran <i>et al</i> [146]	1282 (Images)	610/672 (H/NH)	Images	Acc, Rec, Spe, Prec, F1: 99.48%, 100%, 100%, 99.00%, 99.50%
Yuan <i>et al</i> [147]	431 (Volunteers)	196/235 (H/NH)	System configuration; FV; Clinical variables	Acc: 76.19%

Accuracy (Acc), benign tumor (BT), born iterative method (BIM), double benign tumor (DBT), double tumor (2 T), double malignant (DMT), feature vector (FV), F1-score (F1), healthy (H), intracerebral hemorrhagic stroke (ICH), ischemic stroke (IS), mild Alzheimer's disease (MiAD), no healthy (NH), not available (NA), malignant tumor (MT), one benign and one malignant tumor (BMT), precision (Prec), recall (Rec), sensitivity (Sen), specificity (Spe), single tumor (1 T).

Despite these advances, limitations persist. Although there has been an increase in the variability and complexity of the datasets used, there still is a need for continued efforts to expand these characteristics, as well as the size of the datasets. One possible improvement would be the public availability of datasets used in various studies. This practice has proven beneficial in other fields, as replicability is a critical feature in ML research. Without dataset availability, it becomes impossible to replicate results, which poses a significant barrier to progress in this field.

Another important aspect observed in this scoping review is the frequent use of simulated data, particularly in reconstruction studies, where most works rely on numerical simulations rather than experimental or clinical data. While simulations are essential for initial methodological development, it is critical to validate such approaches using experimental phantoms and/or clinical datasets to ensure their applicability in real-world scenarios. Moreover, simulations—especially in two-dimensional settings—may not fully capture the complexities of real data, such as those present in three-dimensional environments with more pronounced multipath effects. These discrepancies highlight the need for caution when interpreting results from simulated data and emphasize the importance of progressive validation stages in future research.

Even with these limitations, some studies have integrated ML with MWI systems like MammoWave or Wavelia, as shown in Rana *et al* (2021) [87] and Fasoula *et al* (2021) [88], respectively, presenting promising results. These findings further suggest the potential of this field. Such cases emphasize the importance of confirming results obtained with phantoms and simulations through *in vivo* studies, highlighting the need for a collective effort in preclinical and clinical research.

Another key takeaway from this scoping review is the importance of using appropriate metrics for the classification tasks being performed. Although the most reported metric in the reviewed studies, accuracy may not always be the best measure to evaluate models. For instance, in classification tasks distinguishing between H and NH cases, minimizing false negatives is often more critical than minimizing false positives. In such cases, sensitivity becomes more significant than accuracy. It is also important to note that, in some cases, a single metric may not suffice to evaluate how effectively the model performs the task. In such instances, employing a set of complementary metrics is recommended to provide a more comprehensive assessment of the model's overall performance. In addition, evaluating model generalization would benefit from the regular use of cross-validation, along with reporting the average and standard deviation of the evaluation metrics, as this would illustrate the model's behavior when retrained on different subsets of data.

In tasks that classify malignant versus benign conditions (e.g. in brain or breast cancer), when the dataset is balanced, accuracy—despite providing useful information about model performance—should be complemented with additional metrics such as sensitivity and specificity to offer a more complete evaluation. Furthermore, accuracy can be misleading when models are trained on unbalanced datasets. In such cases, a model may become 'lazy', achieving high accuracy simply by favoring the majority class, while performing poorly in identifying the minority class. This behavior significantly reduces its utility in real-world applications. Therefore, the F1-score is often a more appropriate metric in these situations, as it accounts for both precision and recall, offering a more balanced assessment of model performance.

Additionally, challenges were encountered in obtaining complete information from the papers, as seen in the tables summarizing dataset details, particularly in the 'Dataset size' and 'Type of sample'.

5. Conclusion

In summary, this article highlighted the advancements and challenges associated with the use of MWI and ML in various medical applications. The results presented in the literature suggest great potential for these techniques but also emphasize the need for additional efforts to overcome limitations related to model complexity and realism, the diversity of tested data, validation with *in vivo* data, and the selection of appropriate metrics depending on the task at hand. It is crucial to acknowledge that while this field has significant potential in medical applications, there is still room for improvement. Collaboration within the scientific community remains vital to achieve the shared goal of improving diagnostic conditions, aiding diagnoses as early as possible.

Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available upon reasonable request from the authors.

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